

TRANS

lighthouses

MORE THAN GREEN

Lighthouses
of transformative
nature-based solutions
for inclusive communities

Funded by
the European Union

Deliverable 1.7

Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan v2

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

CDE: Communication, dissemination and exploitation

EC: European Commission

EEAB: External Ethical Advisory Board

EU: European Union

GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2016/679) KPI: Key Performance Indicator

KER: Key Exploitable Result

KPI: Key Performance Indicators

NBS: Nature Based Solutions

SMEs: Small and Medium-sized Enterprises WP: Work Package

LKLs: Living Knowledge Labs

Purpose of deliverable

This document presents the second iteration of the Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan (Deliverable 1.7) for the TRANS-lighthouses project. Building upon, updating and reviewing the initial CDE plan (D1.1) and the dissemination package (D1.3) developed during the first phase of the project. This updated plan arrives at month 30 of the project's 42-month timeline. This critical mid-to-late stage transition point allows us to integrate lessons learned and refine project strategies, and enhance the impact of communication, dissemination and exploitation for the remaining project period.

In short, this updated plan details and evaluates how the TRANS-lighthouses consortium organizes its efforts to:

- Effectively communicate the project's objectives, activities, and findings.
- Strengthen interactions and collaborations among consortium members.
- Disseminate knowledge to relevant audiences.
- Maximize the exploitation of project results for broader societal benefit.

- What has changed?

The primary objectives of this updated Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan is to update the initial CDE plan. While the core purpose of the plan remains the same, this updated version also documents the progress made in the project so far and assesses it against the original strategy outlined in D1.1. This will provide a clear account of achievements, challenges, and adaptations made during implementation. This assessment serves both as a mechanism for accountability and as a learning opportunity to further improve communication efforts moving forward. Secondly, to present a refined strategy based on implementation experience, stakeholder feedback, and the continuously evolving needs of the project. The updated strategy reflects lessons from implementation; keeping and building on effective approaches while adjusting others to ensure that communication efforts truly support the project's goals.

- Why were these changes made?

The core purpose of the plan remains to guide communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities. However, this update was necessary to:

- **Reflect current status.** Update the plan to reflect the project's current status and future direction at the 30-month mark.
- **Ensure accountability and learning.** The assessment of progress against D1.1 serves both as a mechanism for accountability to funding authorities and as a crucial learning opportunity to further improve communication efforts moving forward.
- **Optimize for the remaining project period.** By integrating implementation experience and stakeholder feedback, the plan is refined to ensure that communication efforts are as effective and impactful as possible for the remaining duration of the project.

- Resulting outcomes

These revisions are designed to achieve several key outcomes for the project and its stakeholders:

- **Clear account of achievements.** Provide a transparent, section by section, overview of the project's successes and the evolution of its CDE strategy.
- **Improved strategic alignment.** Ensure that CDE efforts are continuously aligned with project goals and adapt to emerging needs.

- **Enhanced engagement.** Offer a more accessible and relevant document for primary audiences, including the European Commission, the TRANS-lighthouses consortium and associated partners, and external stakeholders.
- **Facilitate learning.** Enable both the consortium and external stakeholders to learn from the project's experiences and lessons.

Highlights of key achievements (M6 - M30)

Since the initial plan (D1.1), the TRANS-lighthouses project has made considerable progress in implementing its communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities. This updated plan provides an element of reporting on the progress, successes, challenges, and adaptations made during this period.

The table below highlights some of the projects major CDE achievements;

Expanded its digital presence and engagement:	The project has exceeded the targets set out in the Grant agreement regarding its digital presence. This includes notable growth in website traffic, social media reach, and newsletter subscriptions. The communication efforts have led to all KPIs related to digital presence having been reached and surpassed, which indicates effective outreach to target audiences.
Organized and participated in numerous events:	These events, ranging from consortium meetings, scientific conferences, and local public events, have facilitated knowledge exchange, collaboration, and raised awareness about the project's objectives and findings.
Developed and disseminated a variety of communication materials:	The project has developed and disseminated a variety of communication materials, including policy briefs, educational videos, and serious games, tailored to different stakeholder categories and communication contexts, to translate its key research findings into tangible outcomes with broader societal and political impact (see KPIs, section 3.3).
Strengthened internal communication and collaboration:	Regular consortium meetings and the use of collaborative platforms have created a foundation for consistent collaboration and coordinated efforts across all work packages since the beginning of the project.
Successful implementation & consistent use of monitoring tools:	The CDE monitoring tools developed at the beginning of the project have been a key factor in the successful coordination of CDE efforts (see section 3.4).
Reached the KPI target	In this updated CDE plan, all 78 KPIs have been thoroughly reviewed. The majority of targets have been successfully met, with several exceeding the expected performance levels.

Table 1: Highlights of key achievements.

Methodology for updating the *Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan*

The development of this updated plan followed a systematic approach undertaken to ensure relevance and accuracy. The approach is rooted in a collaborative and iterative process, integrating both retrospective analysis and forward-looking adjustments, which encompassed several key steps:

- 1. Review of Deliverables D1.1 and D1.3.** The process began with a thorough review of existing foundational documents, specifically Deliverables D1.1 (Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan), and secondly, D1.3 (Dissemination Package).
- 2. Section-by-section assessment and adjustment.** Each section of the communication plan underwent a careful assessment. This involved reviewing the original text from D1.1 and structured notes of all necessary adjustments needed. These notes were organized in a section-by-section table including: Status, action, description of changes needed and responsible person (See table 2 below.)
 - The primary focus of these adjustments was to transition from preliminary plans and strategies to reflect implemented plans and actual strategies. Following these revisions, a status report and evaluation were added at the end of each relevant section, providing a clear overview of the progress and impact.
- 3. Collection of data and metrics.** To ground the updated plan in actual performance, a range of data and metrics were collected. This included digital media analytics (social media, website, newsletter). The Key performance indicators (KPIs) were also carefully evaluated one by one. This collection of both quantitative and qualitative data offered clear insights into effectiveness of various communication activities.
- 4. Collaborative development and reflexive monitoring approach.** A collaborative evaluation process was central to developing the deliverable, helping ensure that the updated plan is robust, accurate, and adapted to the project's evolving needs. This process included:
 - *Partner consultation and input:* Consultation with relevant project partners ensured that diverse perspectives and practical experiences were integrated into the plan. Their input was crucial to accurately develop the status reports and to evaluate the KPIs.
 - *Review process:* The updated plan underwent review by the communication experts from the institution of the coordination team and the principal investigator. This multi-layered review process ensured alignment with overall project objectives and adherence to quality standards.

- Checklist used for updating Communication, dissemination, and exploitation plan section-by-section

Status	Sub-Chapter	Action	Details	Responsible¹
Progress codes: Green - Done; Yellow - In progress; Purple - Assigned; Blue - Needs assistance, not assigned.				
Done	Tables/ figures	-	Check Check and update any new tables and figures	Comms coordinator
Done	Executive summary	-	Rewrite This section needs to be rewritten to reflect the content of Version 2. Keep: The core purpose of the plan. Add: - A summary of the implementation progress of communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities since Version 1. - Highlights of key achievements and impacts. - A summary of any significant changes or Updates to the strategy for the rest of the project.	Comms coordinator
Chapter 1. Project Overview				
Done	1.1 Abstract		Keep Keep as is	-
Done	1.2 Consortium		Review & Update Review and Update the list of partners if there have been any changes.	Comms coord., PI, assigned partner.
Done	1.3 Ambition & approach		Keep Keep as is	-
Done	1.4 Objectives & work plan		Keep Keep as is	-
Done	1.5 Assessment & pilot cases		Review Review and Update the list of assessment & pilot cases if there have been any changes.	Review by PI
Done	1.6 Stakeholder analysis		Review Review any potential updates or additions..	Review by PI
Chapter 2. Communication, dissemination and exploitation of results				
Done	2.1 Definitions		Keep Keep mostly as is: Rename <i>Preliminary definitions</i> -> <i>Definitions</i>	-
Done	2.2 Objectives & measures..		Keep Keep as is	-
Done	2.3 Key activities, target		Review Review the table and potentially update it with any new activities, target audiences, channels, or tools that have been identified or used since D1.1.	Comms coord

¹ The names listed under the column of 'Responsible Person' have been changed to titles to adhere to data collection guidelines.

Status	Sub-Chapter		Action	Details	Responsible ¹
	audiences, channels & tools			Implementation Status & Results: Covered in section 3.3. <i>Key performance indicators and key exploitable results</i>	
Done	2.4 narrative, messages & language	241 Brand	Keep	Keep the brand identity information as is (Table 15, 16).	
Done		242 Comms. templates and materials	Review & Update	Update: table of materials and templates (Table 17) with any new templates/materials created since V.1. Provide links to examples in an annex.	Comms coord
Assigned		243 Comms adapted to the local contexts	Review & Update	For each WP: provide a brief progress report on the communication and interaction activities undertaken. -> status reports drafted based on impact reports in PR1. WP leaders tagged to review, edit and add any updates since PR1 in the WP explanations and status reports	Comms coord., WP leaders
Done		244 Events & publications	Update & add	Update: the list of events, list of publications Status report: Include tracking sheets	Comms coord.
Done		245 Digital strategy	Update	Internal platforms & cloud: Briefly confirm that these are still in use and effective, Website: Report how content is being managed and updated, any changes or additions. Social Media: Confirm which social media platforms are actively used. Add analytics: For each active platform, report on key metrics (followers, engagement rate, reach, etc.).	Comms coord.
Done		246 Awareness raising & guidelines	Update & report	For each subsection (Images and messaging, Gender, Sustainability, Accessibility), report on how these guidelines have been implemented in practice. Provide specific examples of ethical, gender-sensitive, sustainable, and accessible communication in the project.	Comms coord., Assigned partner
Chapter 3. Monitoring & evaluation					
Done	3.1 Reflexive monitoring		Update & report	Report on the outcomes and lessons of reflexive monitoring. What has been learned, and how has it influenced the CDE plan?	Comms coord.
	3.2 Revision & Updates		Update & report	Report on the outcomes of the communications survey (Table 35) and the workshop. How has this informed the Updated plan?	Who, where?
Done	3.3 PR1 implementation		Create	Add a new section: Collect all the recommendations from PR1 (review meeting and comments from PO and analyze on implementation.	Comms coord.
In progress	3.3 KPI		Update & report	Update table: Add a new column for "status and progress reporting", and review the KPIs one by one. The majority of the rows completed by comms coord.; A few require assistance from relevant partners (marked in yellow).	Comms coord., PI, assigned partners
Done	3.4 Monitoring tools		Update & report	Review: whether monitoring tools (Table 37) are in use and effective. Briefly describe how they have supported reporting.	
Assigned	3.5 Assessment frameworks	351 Gender	Review & report	Merge: these 3 sections into sub-sections of chapter 2.4.6 - <i>Awareness raising and development of guidelines</i>	Comms coord., assigned partner

Status	Sub-Chapter		Action	Details	Responsible ¹
Who?		352 Sustainability		- Report on the use of the assessment frameworks for gender, sustainability, and accessibility. What have we learned from these assessments?	Comms coord., assigned partner
Who?		353 Accessibility			Comms coord., PI
Chapter 4. Risk assessment, ethics compliance, and data privacy					
37 Done 38.Not	4.1 Risk assessment		Review & report	Review: Communications critical risks (<i>Table 38</i>) SWOT analysis (<i>Table 39</i>).	Comms coord.
Done	4.2 Ethics compliance		Review & report	Report on the activities of the External Ethical Advisory Board (EEAB). Confirm that all ethical procedures are being followed.	Assigned partner
Done	4.3 Data privacy		Review & report	Confirm that the data management plan is being followed and that all data is being handled in compliance with GDPR.	Assigned partner
Chapter 5. Responsible partners and resources					
Done			Review	Review and Update the table of responsible partners and resources (<i>Table 40</i>) to reflect any changes in roles or resource allocation.	Comms coord., PI

Table 2: Section by section planning of D1.7.

Executive Summary

This Executive Summary provides a high-level overview of Deliverable 1.7, the second iteration of the TRANS-lighthouses project's Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation (CDE) Plan. Building on the strategic evolution detailed in the 'Purpose of Deliverable' section, this summary outlines the document's structure and key updates, reflecting the project's progress. The report is structured into five key sections: Project Overview, Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Results, Monitoring and Evaluation, Responsible Partners and Resources, and Risk Assessment, Ethics Compliance, and Data Privacy.

The updated plan continues to be underpinned by the core objectives of the TRANS-lighthouses project, focusing on living knowledge co-construction, knowledge sharing, and synergies building. These objectives are operationalized across all work packages and guide the project's communication efforts. Therefore, the plan is based on the following **8 objectives mirrored in the work plan**:

1. Raise awareness about the project's activities and results;
2. Showcase the plurality of models, strategies and findings from a diversity of contexts;
3. Co-disseminate living knowledges;
4. Bring science to citizens and policy makers;
5. Develop roadmaps, tools and capacity building for co-governance innovations towards co-creation of nature-based solutions (NBS);
6. Achieve visibility in the local communities and document the process of local actions;
7. Better communicate the science of NBS, by supporting citizens' local knowledges and enhancing mutual trust;
8. Potentialize research data and knowledge in terms of intellectual property.

- Overview of document structure and updates

This updated version of the plan (D1.7, Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan v2) builds significantly upon the preliminary strategies outlined in D1.1. While D1.1 established the foundational elements, D1.7 evolved into a more comprehensive and operational document, integrating mechanisms for ongoing status reporting and evaluation across various sections. The document is structured into five key parts, each addressing a critical aspect of the project's communication, dissemination, and exploitation strategy.

The first section 'Project overview' remains largely consistent with D1.1, continuing to provide a stable foundation by detailing the TRANS-lighthouses project's abstract, consortium composition, ambition, approach, objectives, work plan, assessment and pilot cases, and a comprehensive stakeholder analysis. This initial section, identifying seven categories of stakeholders and their communication preferences, serves as a consistent backdrop for the plan's evolution.

However, the subsequent sections, while still containing much of the preliminary plans from D1.1, also demonstrate how the communication, dissemination and exploitation efforts have been implemented. While D1.1 defined objectives, activities, target audiences, channels, tools, and narrative development, D1.7 additionally introduces a critical layer of implementation and assessment. This includes:

→ **Status reports & evaluation (M1-M30)**

Each relevant section concludes with a box of information that states the current status, as well as maps any changes or developments.

→ **Enhanced tracking and reporting**

D1.7 emphasizes the development and utilization of tracking tools by the TRANS-lighthouses. These collaborative tools are designed to support the systematic collection of data on dissemination and communication activities, facilitating internal reporting and accountability to the funding authority. This is a significant advancement from D1.1's more general mention of assessment.

→ **Integrated monitoring and evaluation**

Building on the identification of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and Key Exploitable Results (KERs) in D1.1, D1.7 further integrates reflexive monitoring, as set out in Task 6.1. This version highlights real-time insight into project progress and assesses processes against each KPI.

In essence, while D1.1 provided the initial blueprint that D1.7 builds upon, D1.7 transforms the communication, dissemination, and exploitation plan into a living document. It moves beyond preliminary plans to embed practical mechanisms for tracking, evaluating, and continuously improving the project's outreach efforts. Below is a detailed description of each section in this report;

- Detailed section overview

The first part of the plan, "Project overview", remains largely consistent with the original CDE plan (D1.1.) and gives an overview of the TRANS-lighthouses project;

- **1.1. Abstract:** The abstract remains consistent with the project's initial vision and objectives as outlined in D1.1. No modifications were deemed necessary. The core conceptualization of the TRANS-lighthouses project continues to accurately represent its scope and ambition.
- **1.2. Consortium:** The consortium details are subject to periodic review to ensure accuracy. While the core partnership structure is stable, minor adjustments, such as changes in personnel or administrative details within partner organizations, may occur. D1.7 reflects the most current and accurate representation of the project's collaborative network.
- **1.3. Ambition and approach:** The project's ambition and overarching approach have been maintained without alteration. This strategic direction and methodological framework established in D1.1 remain robust and relevant to the project's evolving activities.

- **1.4. Objectives and work plan:** The defined objectives and the comprehensive work plan continue to guide the project's execution. No changes have been made, underscoring the enduring validity and effectiveness of the initial planning.
- **1.5. Assessment cases and pilot cases:** The selection of assessment and pilot cases, critical for the practical application and evaluation of nature-based solutions, has remained unchanged.
- **1.6. Stakeholders analysis: categories, communication preferences and interests:** The stakeholder analysis is a dynamic component, requiring periodic review to ensure its continued relevance.

Secondly, the plan enters in a more specific and detailed way the project's communication, dissemination and exploitation of results. After defining these three aspects, the objectives and corresponding measures are presented, followed by main activities, target audiences, channels and tools, and the development of the project's narrative, messages and language. In respect to the latter, it includes:

- **2.1. Definitions:** The definitions of key terms related to communication, dissemination, and exploitation have been finalized and integrated into the report.
- **2.2. Objectives and measures across project's key results and work packages:** The overarching objectives and the measures designed to track progress across the project's key results and work packages remain unchanged.
- **2.3. Key activities, target audiences, channels and tools:** A reviewed version of key activities, target audiences, communication channels, or tools that have emerged or been adopted since the initial plan (D1.1). The implementation status and results for these activities are cross-referenced with Section 3.3, which focuses on Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and Key Exploitable Results (KERs).
- **2.4. Narrative, messages and language:**
 - **2.4.1. Brand:** The project's brand identity, as detailed in Table 12 and Table 13, has been established and maintained. This consistency in branding has and is continuously ensuring a recognizable and unified presence across all communication materials and platforms.
 - **2.4.2. Communication templates and materials:** The inventory of communication templates and materials (*Table 17*) has been reviewed and updated to include any new resources developed since D1.1.
 - **2.4.3. Communication and interaction adapted to the local contexts:** Brief progress reports for each workpackage activities, written and reviewed together with Work Package leader in order to ensure that D1.7 accurately reflects the context-specific communication efforts across the project.
 - **2.4.4. Events and publication channels:** The list of events has been updated, and new publications have been added, reflecting the project's dissemination efforts. Tracking sheets are included in the status report, offering a detailed record of participation in events and contributions to scholarly or public discourse.
 - **2.4.5. Digital strategy:** Internal communication platforms and cloud services are confirmed as effective. The website development status is updated, detailing content management processes, structural adherence, and any modifications. The addition of "Website Analytics" and "Social Media analytics" signifies the efforts dedicated towards data-driven monitoring and insights into online engagement. For social media, active platforms have been confirmed, and the assessment has been updated with new insights.

- **2.5. Awareness raising, development and implementation of guidelines:** This chapter reports on the integration of ethical, gender-sensitive, sustainable, and accessible communication guidelines into project practice. For each of these four areas (Images and messaging, Gender, Sustainability, Accessibility), the report evaluates the status of guideline implementation. The section has been significantly restructured to emphasize its importance. First, to enhance visibility, it was promoted from sub-sub-chapter 2.4.6 (in D1.1) to its own dedicated sub-chapter. Second, the section now incorporates the content of sub-chapter 3.5, "Assessment frameworks," from D1.1. This merger simplifies the structure, as the three assessment frameworks previously in 3.5 were specifically for gender, sustainability, and accessibility. Combining them with the corresponding guideline reports in Section 2.5 creates a more logical and coherent presentation of the evaluation and assessment tools.

The third section details and evaluates the assessment of the communication, dissemination, and exploitation efforts. It outlines the project's monitoring and evaluation framework, detailing the reflexive processes, key performance tracking, and systematic revisions.

- **3.1. Reflexive monitoring:** Reflexive monitoring has been actively conducted, providing valuable insights into the project's CDE activities. The report details the outcomes of this monitoring process, highlighting key learnings and how these have directly influenced the CDE plan. This iterative approach ensures that the strategy is not static but evolves based on real-world implementation experiences,
- **3.2. Revision and updates:** A key aspect of revisions made to the projects CDE efforts is based on the first periodic review, which is outlined in the following sub-sections;
 - **3.2.1. Implementation of evaluator comments from PR1:** A new section has been created to specifically address the implementation of evaluator comments from Project Review 1 (PR1). This highlights the project's responsiveness to external feedback and its dedication to continuous improvement. By systematically addressing these comments, thematically organized into 'communication', 'dissemination', and 'exploitation', the project ensures that its CDE plan is robust, comprehensive, and aligned with best practices and external recommendations.
- **3.3. Key performance indicators and key exploitable results:** The Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and Key Exploitable Results (KERs) are central to measuring the project's impact. The table outlining them has been updated with an additional column for "status and progress reporting," providing a clearer overview of achievements against defined metrics. This detailed tracking ensures accountability and transparency in demonstrating the project's progress and potential for exploitation. References of this reporting can be found in the Appendix section.
- **3.4. Monitoring tools:** The monitoring tools (*Table 37*) have been confirmed as effective and are actively in use. The report provides a brief description of how these tools have supported the reporting process, ensuring that data collection and analysis are systematic and reliable.

The fourth section is composed of 3 parts, which have all been evaluated and updated. It addresses and evaluates the risk assessment, ethics compliance, and data privacy within the project.

- **4.1. Risk assessment:** The section starts with a short narrative description of general risks and how they are addressed. Secondly, the communications critical risks (*Table 38*) and the SWOT analysis (*Table 39*) have both been evaluated. This reassessment ensures that potential

challenges to the CDE plan are identified and mitigation strategies are in place. The SWOT analysis, based on the communications survey 1 (September 2023), provided a comprehensive understanding of the partners' dissemination capacity.

- **4.2. Ethics compliance:** This section evaluates the ethical compliance procedures throughout the project. The EEAB plays a crucial role in safeguarding the project's ethical integrity, and this report section outlines how all activities related to communication and dissemination adhere to the highest ethical standards.
- **4.3. Data privacy:** This section has been reviewed and confirms adherence to the data management plan and compliance with GDPR. This is a critical aspect of responsible project management, especially concerning communication and dissemination activities that may involve personal data. The report ensures that all data handling practices are secure, transparent, and fully compliant with regulatory requirements, thereby protecting the privacy of individuals involved in or affected by the project.

The fifth and final section of this CDE plan presents an updated version of the initial overview of roles, responsibilities, and corresponding resources among partners (originally outlined in D1.1). The information on responsible partners and resource allocation (Table 40) has been reviewed and revised to ensure that D1.7 accurately reflects any changes in roles, responsibilities, or resource distribution since the previous version, including:

- project coordinator;
- steering committee;
- work package 6 participants (communication and interaction approaches, pathways, channels and tools adapted to local contexts);
- group of communications contact persons (identified by each partner);
- local partners of pilot cases and of assessment cases;
- associated partners (non-EU);
- all partners (art. 17 of Grant Agreement, transversal operationalisation, monitoring, inform and share).

Roles and objectives in relation to other work packages

This deliverable has a strong connection and builds upon two earlier deliverables in particular;

Firstly, deliverable 1.1 served as a foundation to D1.7. D1.1 established the initial communication, dissemination, and exploitation strategy for the project. The initial strategy defined the project's communication objectives, brand identity, channels, activities, and target audiences. It also sets preliminary key performance indicators (KPIs) and initial risk assessment for communication activities. As an early-stage deliverable, D1.1 was necessarily theoretical and anticipatory, based on projected rather than actual implementation experience.

Secondly, deliverable 1.3 (Dissemination package), which complemented D1.1 by providing a practical dissemination package needed to implement the strategy outlined in D1.1. D1.3 includes concrete communication and dissemination materials, templates, and practical applications for the project's visual identity. D1.3 focused primarily on tools and resources rather than strategic direction or performance assessment.

D1.7 serves as both an assessment of the progress of implementation and a strategic refinement based on the project's experience, bridging the gap between initial planning and final execution. The table below summarizes the connection between the deliverables;

Key Functions of D1.7 in Relation to D1.1:	Key Functions of D1.7 in Relation to D1.3:
D1.7 evaluates the effectiveness of the strategy outlined in D1.1.	D1.7 assesses the effectiveness of dissemination tools and resources.
D1.7 updates and refines the strategy based on lessons learned from the implementation.	D1.7 identifies improvements to the dissemination package.
D1.7 creates a continuity by maintaining strategic consistency with D1.1.	D1.7 connects practical tools with strategic direction.

Table 3: Key Functions of D1.7 in Relation to D1.1 and D1.3.

While deliverable 1.7 is comprehensive in its coverage of communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities, we acknowledge certain boundaries and limitations. The intent of this deliverable is not to replace specialized technical documentation (e.g. for specific tools or platforms) or work package-specific dissemination strategies. Rather, its purpose is to offer an overarching strategic framework that helps coordinate the work package specific activities with the project's overall goals.

Finally, this deliverable should be read in conjunction with deliverable 1.8 the Data Management Plan (which has also been updated at month 30). D1.8 addresses specific aspects of research data sharing and open access implementation. Together, these documents provide a comprehensive framework for maximizing the visibility, accessibility, and impact of the project's activities and results.

Project Overview

1. Project overview

1.1. Abstract

The TRANS-lighthouses project aims to understand the strengths and limitations in the design and implementation of nature-based solutions. Based on material and immaterial evidence, it proposes to contribute to rethinking and reframing the main elements that compose the complexity of creating socially and ecologically just solutions.

As a project funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe programme (grant agreement 101084628), lasting from May 2023 to October 2026 and with a budget 5.9 million euros, TRANS-lighthouses strengthens socio-politics as part of the public agenda for nature-based solutions towards systemic change.

TRANS-lighthouses also integrates a network of "lighthouses" in urban, rural, coastal and forest areas. The "lighthouses" are a metaphor for a set of local governance arrangements and instruments, within multi-stakeholder networks and concerted groups.

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101084628>

Figure 1: CORDIS profile

They are aimed at improving the contributions of nature-based solutions and achieving, in an integrated way, ecological, social and economic objectives. To this end, new governance models are being tested, as well as approaches and tools for co-creation in small scale but big picture projects that can be upscaled over time.

Accordingly, each lighthouse is composed of living knowledge labs, assessment cases, pilot cases and international associated partners. In these spaces, the interaction of different knowledges, experiences and roles support the assessment of ongoing solutions and the testing of new ones. In this way, it is intended to prioritise the perspectives of citizens, in dialogue with other interested actors for their co-creation.

Figure 2: TRANS-lighthouses map

1.2. Consortium

The consortium of TRANS-lighthouses project comprises research and innovation performing organisations, policy-making institutions and civil society organisations, with 19 European partners from 10 countries. In terms of international cooperation, TRANS-lighthouses also integrates 9 associated partners from 7 countries in the Americas, Africa and Asia.

Table 4: EU participants

International cooperation / Associated partners

LATIN AMERICA		AFRICA	
ACADEMIA – Universidad de Chile, Universidad de Buenos Aires, Universidade de Brasília, Rede RIU CITIES – Prefeitura de São Paulo <i>Chile, Argentina, Brazil</i>		ACADEMIA – University of Dar es Salaam CSOs – Polycom Development Project <i>Tanzania, Kenya</i>	
NORTH AMERICA		ASIA	
ACADEMIA – University of Illinois <i>USA</i>		ACADEMIA – Tata Institute of social sciences <i>India</i>	

Universidad de Chile CL	Chile
Instituto de Investigaciones G. Germani Facultad de Ciencias Sociales Universidad de Buenos Aires	Argentina
Periférico Trabalhos Emergentes	Brazil
Supervisão Para Assuntos de Governo Aberto (Open Government Department of São Paulo City Hall)	Brazil
Tata Institute of Social Sciences	India
The Board of Trustees of the University of Illinois	USA
University of Dar es Salaam	Tanzânia
Polycom Development Project	Kenya
Universidade Estadual de Ponta Grossa	Brazil

Table 5: Associated partners

1.3. Ambition and approach

The project's ambition is to become a European reference in terms of socio-political challenges, in order to locally support nature-based projects and solutions. The assessment of the benefits and effects of solutions already developed aims to recognize practices and disseminate more economically and socially fair guidelines for their implementation.

Therefore, the acronym of the project TRANS-lighthouses stands for:

MORE THAN GREEN - Lighthouses of transformative nature-based	
T ransformative	contributing to the full potential of NBS with communities
R eflexive	grounded in assessment and critical analysis
A ctivist	aiming at socioeconomic and political changes
N etworked	acting together across borders, disciplines and sectors
S olutions	multidimensional and nature-based governance
lighthouses	leading research in action

Table 6: Acronym

Conceptual approach

Network – diversity & community of practice	Network of NBS' lighthouses for inclusive communities, in urban, rural, coastal and forested areas, bringing together a diversity of European and international partners.
Interlinking metaphor – enhancing NBS contributions	Metaphor for a set of local arrangements and instruments grounded on a concerted and networked group of multiple actors committed to enhancing NBS contributions towards interlinked ecological, social and economic targets.
Testing small scale, but big-picture projects	Approach for testing new governance models and co-creation approaches and tools on small scale but big-picture projects that can be upscaled over time.
Living knowledge labs, assessment cases, pilot cases & international observers	Dedicated to assessing ongoing NBS and testing new ones, prioritising the perspectives of citizens and stakeholders for valuing and co-creating NBS.

Table 7: Conceptual approach

1.4. Objectives and work plan

Objectives	
	<p>1. GATHERING transdisciplinary perspectives through North-South community of practice</p> <hr/> <p>2. EXPANDING NBS definition through a reflexive framework to recognize diverse forms of knowledge</p> <hr/> <p>3. UNDERSTANDING the range of potential and limitations in NBS design and implementation</p> <hr/> <p>4. POLITICISING governance for just transition</p> <hr/> <p>5. EMBEDDING co-creation processes into governance arrangements</p> <hr/> <p>6. GUIDING an engaged and transformative communication</p> <hr/>

Table 8: Project's objectives

Work plan / Work packages

Work packages	Leading partner
1 Project and consortium management Overall coordination of the work plan and consortium / Gender+ dimension	CES-UC Portugal
2 Living knowledge co-production and Place-based research Expanding the conventional approaches to NBS by developing reflexive and critical frameworks	RUC Denmark
3 Research in action and assessment Research, assessment and deepening the analysis of social, political and cultural contexts.	TUM Germany
4 Innovative governance for NBS co-creation Gathering partners with experience in research and intervention regarding participatory models of governance	CES-UC Portugal
5 Pilot cases implementation through co-creation Interconnects the research activities with real-world co-creation cases	Cyl Cyprus
6 Community-based communication and citizen science Communication and interaction with citizens in the deployment of NBS	CES-UC Portugal
7 Ethics requirements Sets out the 'ethics requirements' the project must comply with	CES-UC Portugal

Table 9: Work plan / Work packages

1.5. Assessment cases and pilot cases

Assessment cases			Pilot cases		
Location	Connecting lighthouses	Leading partner	Location	Connecting lighthouses	Leading partner
Brussels / Belgium	>	Brussels	Brussels / Belgium	>	Brussels
Bologna / Italy	>	Sapienza	Rome / Italy	>	Sapienza
Troodos / Cyprus	>>	Cyl	Strovolos / Cyprus	>>	Cyl
Estarreja / Portugal	>	CME	Estarreja / Portugal	>	CME
Barcelos / Portugal	>>	CMB	Barcelos / Portugal	>>	CMB
Lagoa / Portugal	>>	UAc	Azores / Portugal	>>>	UAc
Regenerative farming network / Denmark	>	RUC	Regenerative farming network / Denmark	>	RUC
Madrid / Spain	>>	UEx	Cáceres / Spain	>>	EBR
Upper Allgäu / Germany	>	TUM		>>>>	

Table 10: Assessment and pilot cases

1.6. Stakeholders analysis: categories, communication preferences and interests

Stakeholders categories	Communication preferences and interests
Project teams, partners, associated partners and observers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → share information, updates, and resources → potential partners and collaborators from other countries and projects
Researchers, scientists, students and educators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → project's findings → methodologies → opportunities for collaboration → educational components and resources → workshops → training opportunities
Funding agencies and stakeholders in general	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → project's updates → progress reports → financial information → project's outcomes
Policy makers, government officials, local authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → alignment with EU policies and priorities → project's impact on policy development
Media and journalists	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → public awareness and media coverage of the project → easy access to press releases, and media resources → contact information for media inquiries
Citizens, local communities, and general public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → educational resources → outreach materials → information on the societal benefits of the research
Civil society organisations, SMEs, social enterprises, and practitioners	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → project's innovations → project's technologies → potential for partnerships

Table 11: Stakeholders categories, communication preferences and interests

Communication, dissemination and exploitation of results

2. Communication, dissemination and exploitation of results

2.1. Definitions

	Communication	Dissemination	Exploitation
What	Inform, promote and communicate activities and results	Make knowledge and results publicly available free-of-charge	Make concrete use of results for commercial, societal and political purposes
For whom	Citizens, stakeholders and the media	Who can learn and benefit from the results, such as: scientists, industry, public authorities, policymakers, civil society	Who can take the results forward or invest in them, such as: researchers, stakeholders, industry (also SMEs), public authorities, policymakers, civil society
How	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Having a well-designed strategy > Conveying clear messages > Using the right channels 	Publishing results in: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Scientific magazines; > Scientific and/or targeted conferences > Databases 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Creating roadmaps, prototypes, software > Sharing knowledge, skills, data
When	From the start until the end of the action	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Anytime, as soon as results become available > Up to four years after the end of the project 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Towards the end of the action and beyond, as soon as exploitable results are available > Up to four years after the end of the project
Ks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Project's key result: key tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected, which are generated in the action as well as any attached rights, including intellectual property rights. > Key Performance Indicator (KPI): quantifiable indicator of progress toward a specific objective and/or intended result. > Key Exploitable Result (KER): identified main interesting result which has been selected and prioritised due to its high potential to be "exploited" - meaning to make use and derive benefits - downstream the value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an important input to policy, further research or education. Criteria: a) degree of innovation; b) exploitability; c) impact. 		

Table 12: Communication, dissemination, exploitation, results and indicators
Adapted from European Commission, 2023 & Horizon Results Platform

2.2. Objectives and measures across project's key results and work packages

The plan for communication, dissemination and exploitation of results is strategically underpinned by the core of the TRANS-lighthouses' objectives in terms of living knowledge co-construction, knowledge sharing and synergies building, being transversely operationalized across the work packages. Therefore, the plan is based on the following 8 objectives mirrored in the work plan.

Figure 3: Communication, dissemination and exploitation of results: Objectives

Transversal operationalisation across project's key results work packages		
Project's key results	Objectives and measures	Work packages & tasks
1. The project's successful implementation	<p>→ 1. Raise awareness about the project's activities and results</p> <p>> 1.1. Set out how the consortium organises the communication of the project in terms of image/identity, as well as tools and channels through which awareness is raised about activities and results</p> <p>> 1.2. Coordination, monitoring and appropriation of communication and dissemination tools and channels</p>	Tasks 1.1, 1.5, 1.6 (connection with work package 6)
2. Community of practice	<p>→ 2. Showcase the plurality of models, strategies and findings from a diversity of contexts</p> <p>> 2.1. Involving associated partners in a community of practice</p>	Tasks 1.2, 1.3
3. Expanded conceptual framework and assessment for NBS	<p>→ 3. Co-disseminate living knowledge</p> <p>>3.1. Scientific dissemination of expanded conceptual framework and assessment for NBS</p> <p>>3.2. Developing ways for inclusive knowledge and practice dissemination</p>	Work packages 2 & 3 (connection with work package 6)
4. Science for citizens and policy makers	<p>→ 4. Bring science to citizens and policy makers</p> <p>>4.1. Living no one behind in research</p> <p>>4.2. Providing a space for long-term relationships with policy makers</p>	Tasks 3.3, 3.6 (connection with task 6.5)
5. Co-governance innovations towards co-creation of NBS	<p>→ 5. Develop roadmaps, tools and capacity building for co-governance innovations towards co-creation of NBS</p> <p>>5.1. Production of transition roadmaps for the replication of co-governance methodologies</p> <p>>5.2. Amplifying youth and older adults' involvement with research and guidelines for the co-creation of NBS</p>	Tasks 4.4, 4.5 (connection with task 6.4)
6. Living Knowledge(s) Labs	<p>→ 6. Achieve visibility in the local communities and document the process of local actions</p> <p>>6.1. Communication for social mobilisation and citizen engagement.</p> <p>>6.2. Documentation of local action and practice</p>	Tasks 5.1, 5.2, 5.5 (connection with work package 6)
7. Citizen science global framework for NBS	<p>→ 7. Better communicate the science of NBS, by supporting citizens' local knowledges and enhancing mutual trust</p> <p>>7.1. Developing a citizen science global framework for NBS</p>	Work package 6
8. Research data and knowledge	<p>→ 8. Potentialize research data and knowledge in terms of intellectual property</p> <p>>8.1. Compliance with open access principles</p> <p>>8.2. Management and protection</p> <p>>8.3. Ethics compliance</p>	Work packages 1 & 7, task 2.5

Table 13: Transversal operationalisation

Status report & evaluation of Objectives and measures across project's key results and work packages (M1-M30):

For a detailed report on *Transversal operationalisation across project's key results work packages* see section 3.3. *Key performance indicators and key exploitable results*.

2.3. Key activities, target audiences, channels and tools

#. Project's key results #Work packages & Tasks	Activities	Target audiences	Channels & tools
1. The project's successful implementation → Awareness about activities and results <i>T 1.1, 1.5, 1.6</i> <i>(connection with WP6)</i>	Definition of communication policy, procedures and objectives by the steering committee	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Researchers - Practitioners - Policy makers - Public at large 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - organisation of events (kick-off/closing, conference/school) - public communications/exhibitions/workshops - participation of partners in events
	Design of communication tools to support the development of communication materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consortium members - Associated partners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - brand and application guidelines - communication templates - website, newsletter template, social media accounts - database (images, news, inputs and metrics)
	Development of communication materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Researchers - Practitioners - Policy makers - Local stakeholders, communities and citizens 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - fact sheet/project overview, leaflet/flyer, posters, video - contributions to the project's website and social media posts - bi-annual newsletter - press releases
	Divulgate the project in the websites and newsletters of international networks and stakeholders, traditional media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Researchers - Practitioners - Policy makers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - media appearances (TV/radio) - publications in specialised magazines/journals, blogs
	Development of interactions among consortium members, as well as tools and platforms for project management and team communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consortium members - Researchers - Practitioners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - monthly online meetings of the steering committee - in-person/online consortium meetings, technical visits - monitoring and planning reports by work package - project's workflow and standard quality procedures - Gender Equality and Diversity (GED) focal point - internal communication platform
2. Community of practice → Plurality of models, strategies and findings showcased from a diversity of contexts <i>T 1.2, 1.3</i>	Knowledge sharing and synergies building among partners, and in the framework of clustering activities with other projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consortium members - Researchers - Practitioners - EU funded projects - Associated partners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - internal and/or open webinars - clustering with projects/liaison with networks - collaborations with sibling projects - compilation and analysis on sharing and synergies
	Involving associated partners in a community of practice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consortium members - Associated partners 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - webinars - participation in technical visit and/or consortium event - compilation and analysis on sharing and synergies - publication based on North-South cross comparison
3. Expanded conceptual framework and assessment for NBS → Living knowledge to be co-disseminated <i>WPs 2 & 3</i> <i>(connection with WP 6)</i>	Scientific dissemination of expanded conceptual framework and assessment for NBS carried out by partners in international referenced publications and conferences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Researchers - Practitioners - Policy makers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - papers in international referenced publications - presentations and publications in international and referenced conferences
	Inclusive knowledge and practice dissemination, by means of unconventional initiatives of knowledge sharing, such as local community events, local media, and networks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local stakeholders, communities and citizens - Local networks - Social economy sector 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - local community events of scientific knowledge dissemination - project presentations in local media - clustering and liaison with networks

		- Local and regional business initiatives	
4. Science for citizens and policy makers → Living no one behind in research and long-term relationships <i>T 3.3, 3.6</i> (connection with T 6.5)	Results are shared and made accessible throughout the research process by means of internal living documents	- Consortium members - Local stakeholders, communities and citizens	- internal living documents - translation into local languages
	Democracy labs	- Policy makers: local government officials, politicians - Practitioners: civil society organisations, municipal staff - Researchers	- organisation of democracy labs - policy briefs, infographics, videos and serious gaming
5. Co-governance innovations towards co-creation of NBS → Replication and amplification <i>T 4.4, 4.5</i> (connection with T 6.4)	Production of transition roadmaps for the replication of co-governance methodologies and the facilitation of enabling environments for co-creation of NBS	- Local stakeholders, communities and citizens, local organisations, SMEs, social enterprises - Policy makers: politicians - Practitioners: civil society organisations, municipal staff - Researchers	- roadmaps disseminated through workshops for co-governance, policy briefs, videos and serious gaming (see democracy labs activities and outputs)
	Development of research and guidelines to amplify the involvement of youth and older adults in the co-creation of NBS	Local stakeholders, communities and citizens, in particular youth, older adults, colleges	- dissemination and training workshops with pilots - videos produced by youth - introduction of contents in college disciplines
6. Living Knowledge(s) Labs → Visibility and documentation <i>T 5.1, 5.2, 5.5</i> (connection with WP 6)	The communication strategies for social mobilisation and citizen engagement are devised with the communities and participants, supported by frameworks, guidelines and tools developed in WP6	Local stakeholders, communities and citizens	- establishment and documentation of labs - participatory budgeting processes - graphic and text material about the aims of pilots - adaptations of the communication materials for local use
	The documentation of the overall design and implementation process of the pilot cases applies a cross-medial approach	- Local stakeholders, communities and citizens - Researchers - Practitioners - Policy makers	- co-production of playbook - database with labs' images, news and other relevant communication and dissemination inputs and metrics
7. Citizen science global framework for NBS → Community-based communication and assessment <i>WP 6</i>	Mobilisation of citizens' local knowledges and development of trust: > Reflexive monitoring approach to finetune living global framework, which showcases approaches and pathways > Youth involvement in community-based communication for NBS	Local stakeholders, communities and citizens	- living global framework of citizen science for NBS - portfolio of participatory methods - digital platform co-created with youth, including subsites - social media accounts and media campaigns with youth
	Exploration of data usability and tools (contexts and profiles): > Prototyping accessibility and relevance of results > Digital and low-tech tools to support participatory assessment and to be embedded in the implementation of NBS	- Local stakeholders, communities and citizens - Researchers - Practitioners	- data usability demonstrator - report on digital and low-tech tools building

8. Research data and knowledge → Accessibility, preservation and ethics compliance <i>WPs 1 & 7, T 2,5</i>	Compliance with open access principles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Researchers - Practitioners - Policy makers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - integration of open access principles - resources available on the project's website - publications on open research platforms - publications with free access to readers (afforded fee)
	Management and protection: > Data management plan > Internal collaborative communication tools with restricted access	Consortium members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - regulations in consortium agreement - updated data management plan
	Elaboration and application of ethics requirements: > Principles and procedures established under task 2.5 > Work package 7 covering ethics requirements > Dissemination among consortium members > Ethics documents kept on file and submitted upon request by coordinator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consortium members - Local stakeholders, communities and citizens 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ethics deliverables - ethics board & meetings - activation of focal points and local ethics channels - guidance on research ethics and inclusive participation - webinars for dissemination and appropriation - translation into local languages

Table 14: Key activities, target audiences, channels and tools

Status report & evaluation of Key activities, target audiences, channels and tools (M1-M30)

For a detailed report on key activities, target audiences, channels and tools; see section 3.3. *Key performance indicators and key exploitable results.*

2.4. Narrative, messages and language

2.4.1. Brand

From small-scale/big-picture projects to shining rays

Created by Flatart from Noun Project

From presentation template - [Communications project's database on Basecamp / Templates](#)

From presentation template - [Communications project's database on Basecamp / Templates](#)

From Pictures & Videos database on Basecamp / [Kick-off event - June 2023](#)

Funded by
the European Union

From [Communications project's database on Basecamp / Brand-Logo](#)

From [Download centre for visual elements](#)

Table 15: Brand: from small-scale/big-picture projects to shining rays

> Application guidelines

Brand application guidelines	
Basic usage guidelines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Never change or distort the logo. - Never use different typefaces or colours. - Ensure good logo legibility, namely by using adequate size and colour versions.
Vertical application MAIN	
Horizontal application	
Monochromatic negative versions	<p>To be used when a colour version is not possible.</p>
Colour / negative versions	<p>Anticipating different brand applications, two coloured versions are defined to be used over the following background colours: corporate orange and grey.</p>
Minimum sizes and safety margins	<p>- Usage of logos below the indicated sizes should be avoided.</p> <p>- Also, in order to guarantee good logo legibility, no other visual elements should be present within the specified safety margins</p>
Colour codes	<p> PANTONE Orange 021C CMYK 4 77 100 0 RGB 232 96 36 HEX #e86024 RAL 6018 </p> <p> PANTONE 432 C CMYK 70 54 60 37 RGB 68 79 76 HEX #444f4c RAL 6018 </p>
Logo usage on different colour backgrounds	<p>On coloured backgrounds, the choice of the logo version should always favour the best contrast possible.</p>
Typography	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Raleway - Open Font License - https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Raleway
EU emblem and funding statement art. 17 - Grant agreement	<p>- Use of the EU emblem in communication, displayed prominently and correctly, in combination with a simple funding statement</p> <p>- Ready-to-use funding statements/download centre for visual elements (in all EU languages, and in 14 non-EU languages): https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/information-sources/logo-download-center_en</p> <p>- In publications, reports and more complex written document/materials use also: <i>"Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them".</i></p> <p>Funded by the European Union</p>

From [Communications project's database on Basecamp / Brand-Logo](#)

Table 16: Brand application guidelines

2.4.2. Communication templates and materials

All communication templates and materials are compiled and made accessible to partners on the Basecamp internal collaborative platform: [ITRANS-LI Headquarters > Docs & Files > Communications](#).

As established under task 1.5 on communication and dissemination, the communication templates and materials are produced:

- in such a way that they can be appropriated and adapted by teams for local use and dissemination to target local stakeholders, communities and citizens;
- in English, considering that translation into local languages will be provided by the respective consortium partners (Portugal, Denmark, Germany, Cyprus, France, Belgium, Italy, Spain) and associated partners (Chile, Argentina, Brazil, India, USA, Tanzania, Kenya);
- in consultation with the participants of work package 6 dedicated to community-based communication and citizen science.

Communication templates and materials		Version
Types of material	Purpose / Description / Use / Snapshots	
Institutional profile and messaging	<p>> Project overview included in communication, dissemination and exploitation plan</p> <p>> Basis for the development of fact sheet, leaflet/flyer and posters to support partners in networking activities and public events</p> <p>1. Project overview</p> <p>1.1. Abstract</p> <p>1.2. Consortium</p> <p>1.3. Ambition and approach</p> <p>1.4. Objectives and work plan</p> <p>1.5. Assessment cases and pilot cases</p> <p>1.6. Stakeholders analysis: categories, communication preferences and interests</p>	V1
Template of project presentations	<p>> .ppt file with a summary of the project to be used and adapted by partners in their project presentations</p>	V1

Template of deliverables

> .doc file for the development of deliverables/reports

> It includes guidelines and good practices about:

- formatting possibilities;
- inclusion of information/analysis on communication, dissemination, and exploitation of results, as well as ethical issues foreseen or faced;
- process of collaborative elaboration and definition of authorship and roles;
- font sources and formats.

V1, V2

Posters
- About the project
- Cases

> Project overview to support partners in networking activities and public events

> Consortium, ambition and objectives, approach

> A1 - 594 x 841 mm

> 10 Assessment cases:

- NBS short description
- geographic area
- relevance
- governance
- challenges
- who owns the land
- synergies
- local partners
- SDGs

> 8 Pilot cases

- social characterisation
- motivation
- existing NBS
- leverage resources
- challenges
- governance
- small scale NBS testing
- who owns the land
- synergies
- local partners

V1, V2

Press release and media materials

> Press release #1 developed and adapted by partners to announce the launching of the project

> Other press releases are being developed and shared by partners along the project

> Press releases, media appearances and materials are compiled and made accessible to partners on the Basecamp internal collaborative platform

New European consortium to delve into the socio-political dimensions of nature-based solutions

CES-UC lidera estudo sobre a participação de cidadãos/ãs no desenho de soluções baseadas na natureza

Presentation of research project. 21, 22, 23 June 2023. São Miguel (Azores)

V1

Materials for events

- > Roll-up
 - > Badges
 - > Invitation letter
 - > Certificate of attendance
- Print and digital materials to be reused in all events

V1

Organisation of consortium meetings

- > Booklet of kick-off event
 - > Memory of kick-off event
 - > Agenda of online consortium meetings
 - > Work packages presentations: Reporting & Planning
- Agenda/programme, dynamics, workshops, visits, practical information: formats, methodologies, materials as inspiration and lessons learned for all consortium meetings

- Wrap-up of workshops, roundtables and dynamics
- General assembly minutes
- Assessments
- Attendance sheets
- Presentations
- Materials
- Photos and video recordings

- Programme "Let's get together and get to know each other better!"
 - Overview of the project
 - Practical information

Methodology for Day 1

- **General assembly by work package**, which will accommodate both presentations & roundtables
- Consistent WPs will debate forum in the afternoon
- Consistent WPs with the General Assembly in the afternoon
- Updates and opportunities by work package will focus on the following aspects:
 - 1. Roles and objectives in relation to other work packages (e.g. Framework)
 - 2. Report on advances and updates
 - 3. Planning for the next 4 months
- This topic to the presentations of work packages will be made available before the meeting so you can access the information beforehand to make specific issues you wish to clarify and advance concerning

Proposed schedule for Day 1 (October 24th)

MORNING		AFTERNOON	
09:00-09:30	Welcome	09:30-10:00	WP1 - LINK TO DOCUMENT
09:30-10:00	WP4 - LINK TO DOCUMENT	10:00-10:30	Break
10:00-10:30	WP5 - LINK TO DOCUMENT	10:30-11:00	Break
10:30-11:00	Break	11:00-11:30	WP7 - General Assembly - LINK
11:00-11:30	WP6 - LINK TO DOCUMENT	11:30-12:00	WP8 - LINK TO DOCUMENT
11:30-12:00	WP3 - LINK TO DOCUMENT	12:00-12:30	WP9 - LINK TO DOCUMENT
12:00-12:30	Lunch		

Meeting 1 Video archive that will be available:

- [WP1](#) - [LINK TO DOCUMENT](#)
- [WP2](#) - [LINK TO DOCUMENT](#)
- [WP3](#) - [LINK TO DOCUMENT](#)
- [WP4](#) - [LINK TO DOCUMENT](#)
- [WP5](#) - [LINK TO DOCUMENT](#)
- [WP6](#) - [LINK TO DOCUMENT](#)
- [WP7](#) - [LINK TO DOCUMENT](#)
- [WP8](#) - [LINK TO DOCUMENT](#)
- [WP9](#) - [LINK TO DOCUMENT](#)

Online format: 45mn sessions by work package; Pilots forum; dialogue with sibling projects and associated partners

- Roles and objectives in relation to other work packages
- Reporting: key activities developed; achievements; challenges & shortcomings, improvements needed
- Planning for next 4 months; key activities; interactions with other tasks, WPs, partners; expected results

V1

Padlet

- > Launched at the kick-off event held in June 2023, in Azores as "Photographic Mosaic"
 - > The concept is an inspiring experiment for participants to record their emotions, visions and perspectives
 - > The participants were challenged to take pictures of elements that relate to the acronym of "TRANS-lighthouses"
- To be continued and embedded on the website

V1

<p>Videos</p>	<p>> Video memory: - recorded for the kick-off meeting by partners' teams and edited by Kairós; - to be used on the website for partners' presentation</p> <p>> Other videos have been / are being developed, such as: - documentation of Living Knowledge Labs - democracy labs: webinars, animations - videos produced by youth - institutional video on the project - webinars and conferences</p>		<p>V1</p>			
<p>Database of pictures and videos</p>	<p>> Pictures taken by partners are made available and organised by categories and events.</p> <p>The naming of files include: - what (keywords) - numbering (for similar ones) - who (credit)</p>		<p>V1</p>			
<p>Letterhead template</p>	<p>> Developed based on brand application guidelines</p>	<p>V1, V2</p>				
<p>Digital template of newsletter</p>	<p>> Developed based on: - brand application guidelines - website design</p>	<p>Modelo Trans lighthouses v3</p> <p>V3</p>				

Social media templates

- > Web postcard
- > Digital banner
- Developed based on:
 - brand application guidelines
 - website design

V1, V2

Additional templates developed throughout the project

Digital media templates

- > Social media text content templates
- > Infographic template
- > Updated templates for pilot posters
- > Template for "TRL glossary"

V1, V2, V1

Serious Gaming materials

- > The NBS Board Game (English & Portuguese, French & German under development)
- > Interactive NBS cards (English & Portuguese, French & German under development)
- > PPGIS
- > Spatial Geo-game

V2, V2

<p>Flyer/ leaflet/ brochure</p>	<p>> Project Flyer - One-sided</p> <p>> Project Leaflet -Tri-fold</p>	<p>V1, V1</p>
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Table 17: Communication templates and materials

Status report & evaluation of narrative, messages and language (M1-M30):

Brand and application guidelines have been implemented and are being applied by all partners, with no changes being required. The Communications coordinator oversees and assists partners in the implementation of the brand guidelines whenever needed.

A comprehensive set of materials and templates were developed at the beginning of the project to support communication and dissemination efforts. The majority of materials and templates are continuously and successfully used. A few of the templates/materials have had minor updates (E.g. authorship policy in deliverables template). In Year 2, some new materials/templates were developed based on evolving needs, including social media text content templates, an infographic template, updated templates for pilot posters, and a dedicated template for the 'TRL glossary'²

While a broad range of resources are available, some have not been regularly utilized. This includes Padlet and Zenodo. Further efforts may be needed to encourage the consistent use of these valuable resources. Pictures are regularly shared within the consortium (e.g. on Basecamp, in the project's informal WhatsApp group), while this informal communication is important for sharing updates and strengthening connections and group dynamics, there needs to be strengthened efforts on organizing the photos in the public repository as well. Presentations/participation in events are tracked in *the Dissemination and Communication Tracking spreadsheet*.

²TRL Glossary is a newly developed communications initiative designed to boost the visibility of the project by improving search engine optimization (SEO). Based on keyword research carried out by the communications officer, the glossary responds to a public demand for accessible explanations of key concepts. The glossary functions as a living dictionary of terms central to the project. It is published on the website and repurposed across social media to increase reach and engagement. By answering commonly googled questions and clarifying core project themes, TRL Glossary helps inform a wider audience while improving the project's ranking in search results.

2.4.3. Communication and interaction adapted to the local contexts

> Work Package 6: community-based communication and citizen science

In the framework of work package 6, specific communication and interaction approaches, pathways, channels and tools adapted to the local contexts are also being envisioned.

- The citizen science framework based on reflexive monitoring

Figure 4: Citizen science

Figure 5: Reflexive monitoring process

- Overview of objectives and main approaches

Work package 6: overview and main approaches

Objectives

Pillars

- > Citizen science framework and resources on NBS (task 6.1)
- > Approaches and pathways to social mobilisation and citizen engagement for NBS (task 6.2)
- > Fine-tuning of participatory methods (task 6.3)
- > Design of community-driven communication process based on youth protagonism (task 6.4)
- > Digital and low-tech tools building to support participatory assessment and data usability (task 6.5)

From assessment case to pilot case and from pilot to assessment

- > Starting from
 - existing and previous experiences of the communities
 - expertise and experience of partners
- > Enriched and adapted based on the TRANS-lighthouses scientific and methodological results
- > Through a reflexive participatory monitoring approach anchored in citizen science.

Table 18 : Work package 6: overview and main approaches

- Towards NBS communication: principles, strategies, process

Figure 6: Work package 6: communication principles

Figure 7: Work package 6: development of strategies

Figure 8: Work package 6: community-driven processes

Work Package 6 communications status report & evaluation (M1-M30):

The ongoing implementation of Work Package 6 is having significant impacts on citizen engagement and the co-creation of Nature-Based Solutions. The project's participatory approach, rooted in citizen science, is successfully translating complex NBS concepts into accessible knowledge. The Reflexive Monitoring framework has been particularly impactful, creating a learning environment that stakeholders widely recognized as valuable. The living framework on social mobilization and citizen engagement, documented in Deliverable 6.1, serves as a dynamic resource for pilot case implementation, constantly evolving to meet community needs. Customized participatory methods, including innovative tools like NBS Cards and a Board Game, are effectively tailored to specific pilot cases, enhancing community engagement and governance strategies. Youth empowerment initiatives are successfully positioning young people as change agents, amplifying social mobilization around NBS. The project's communication strategy, outlined in Deliverable 1.1, is ensuring consistent messaging across work packages while adapting to local contexts. The development of both digital and low-tech tools for NBS assessment and monitoring, including a participatory mapping platform (PPGIS) and a catalogue of participatory methods, is enhancing data collection and decision-making processes. Overall, Work Package 6 functions as a bridge between NBS science and society, encouraging the participatory co-design of contextually grounded and inclusive solutions.

> Work Package 5: local communication and documentation of the process

- Local communication platforms for engagement and documentation methods

Aim is to clarify ambiguities, integrate knowledge(s) from a variety of stakeholders, to build on local living knowledge, facilitate acceptance of transformations by the local communities and relevant stakeholders, respond to and address voices that are being heard of.

Specifically the task objective is to:

- Enable community-led mapping of natural resources, ecosystem dynamics, infrastructure pressures, and usage of and impact on culturally significant sites.
- Mobilise local actors in order to incorporate local living knowledge into the planning and implementation of NBS.
- Facilitate participatory documentation during the evaluation of the socio-economic viability of a solution, identifying positive or negative perceptions among the community or dialogue on the potential effects that the NBS may have on the landscape and biodiversity.

It is expected that through these activities we can achieve higher levels of local engagement and knowledge communication than typical dissemination approaches. This task works in tandem with task 3.5, 5.2, 5.3 and 6.5.

Local communication platforms for engagement & documentation methods

Low digital skills documentation process and tools

1. Focus Groups to discuss working over flowchart diagrams with node-link map outputs.
2. Photo-video storyboarding/storywall created by professionals, champions, or through training.
3. Photowalks.
4. Docu-films produced by professionals, champions, or through training and workshops, including semi-structured interviews.

[Documentary film](#) making to document the creation of the NBS pilot and communicate the process and results to mobilise the local communities (2025).

Medium-High digital skills documentation process and tools

1. Serious games (on Actionbound platform) and 3D and multi-sensory documentation of local environments, activities and dynamics by means of multimedia devices (mobile phone camera, voice recorder, sensors) for crowdsourcing of information.

Actionbound gamified crowdsourcing tool, created in T6.5 and T5.3 to support youth engagement and community communication activities while promoting education about the pilot territory biodiversity challenges. (2025).

2. Citizen science tools for crowdsourcing / Mobile apps for citizen science for community building around causes to mobilise local groups and stakeholders.

High digital skills communication and engagement methods and tools

1. Online PPGIS enabled platform for accessing, uploading and sharing georeferenced assets.
2. Visualisation of ecosystem-based adaptation scenarios (impact of climate anomalies or human-technical activities on site, on maps and sketches) created by researchers and disseminated through websites and social media channels.

Translighthouses PPGIS platform User Interface (2025).

Visualising timelines of past and future flooding conditions in Pedieos river in Nicosia based on scientific observation and simulated data.

Table 19: Local communication platforms for engagement & documentation methods

- Workflow: research, documentation, creation

Workflow for local communication and documentation of the process

Desk research

Objective

→ Existing available resources (data, equipment, expertise).

Results

→ Cultural, historical and background research on the context
→ Repository of available resources (data, physical, and immaterial)

Field research

Objective

→ Collect and produce additional data needed for the analysis of the site/ecosystems/neighbourhood

Results

→ New data produced through multiple activities (surveys, participatory mapping, etc.)
→ Spatial basemaps, diagrams and data visualisations.

Spherical images photogrammetric method to 3D reality capture pilot sites and environments.

Documentation stage

1. Communicate Strategic Visioning values.
2. Documenting and communicating living knowledge.
3. Documenting the co-creation process and strategic development scenarios.
4. Document decision making process including dilemmas dialogue, negotiations in participative budgeting sessions.
5. Document reflective processes – assessing the scenarios.
6. Document creative thinking and mutual understanding.

Open data access in CoPaB tool developed in T5,5 for supporting Participatory Budgeting pilot activities in co-design and co-governance (2025)..

Stakeholder workshops for strategic visioning of Strovolos pilot using data-driven interactions at the NOUS Strovolos Hub (2024)

Creation stage

1. Abstraction of documented knowledge(s), results, alternative approaches and procedures.
2. Process, convert and visualise data, knowledge(s) and practices.
3. Create workflows, maps and guidelines.
4. Integrate and present in a structured and comprehensive way in the form of a Playbook.

Table 20: Workflow for local communication and documentation of the process

Work Package 5 communications status report & evaluation (M1-M30):

Localized experiences and knowledge have been communicated to and informed relevant tasks in Work Packages (WP2, WP3, WP4, WP6), aiding them to tailor their frameworks, methods, and tools. Contributions to co-governance models, such as the participatory budgeting geo-tool, have been communicated and playtested within pilot sites and with multiple audiences (youth, experts, residents, etc.). WP5 has been a vital channel for practical, localized information, ensuring that other WPs develop context-specific solutions and that co-governance tools are effectively introduced and tested, as well as to facilitate knowledge transfer across pilots and assessment cases via the Pilots Forum Meeting and between the pilot stakeholder communities.

> Work Package 4: dissemination and replication of co-governance, and amplifying youth involvement

Work package 4 includes among its objectives to: prepare tools and roadmaps for dissemination and replication; and create curricula content regarding co-governance for just transition.

These objectives are specifically related to task 4.4 and 4.5.

→ Task 4.4 - Roadmaps and tools for dissemination and replication of co-governance

- Dedicated to developing roadmaps for supporting citizens, politicians, technicians, researchers, practitioners and members from local organisations towards transition for models of co-governance and for facilitating enabling environments for co-creation of NBS.
- Transition roadmaps are being produced for the replication of co-governance methodologies:
 - 1) across organisations (public, private, associative and community-based);
 - 2) for policy makers and decision makers; and
 - 3) for citizens & members from local organisations.
- These transition roadmaps are being disseminated through workshops for co-governance, policy briefs, videos and serious gaming, contributing to introducing co-governance criteria in policies and local/regional planning processes.

→ Task 4.5 - Capacity-building to amplify youth involvement in re-inventing institutional governance models towards co-creation of NBS

- Dedicated to researching and producing guidelines for the co-creation of NBS by youth, starting by understanding the differences of participation by youth in formal educational contexts and non formal contexts. It researches how the governance models in educational institutions (high school, vocational education and universities) sustain opportunities and initiatives for participation.
- The results from this research helps students to formulate contributions for re-inventing institutional governance models towards co-creation of NBS.
- The local youth groups activated within the T6.4 support the task implementation, through the action youth to identify the singularities from their context and to communicate these themes for broader context.
- The task also introduces NBS co-creation and co-governance content in college disciplines in articulation with scientific partners.

Task 4.4 - Roadmaps and tools for dissemination and replication of co-governance
(inputs from task 5.4)

STAKEHOLDERS CATEGORIES			
OUTPUTS	Policy makers, Government officials, Local authorities; SMEs; Civil society organisations	Students and educators; Civil society organisations	Citizens - young people
Policy Briefs	Policy briefs planned for PR3.		
Videos		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Educational (aimed at children, 4-6 years old; format: storyboard - animated; narrative: revival of the human-nature relationship/ Eco-literacy) - Inspiring (aimed at children and young people, 7-12 years old; format: digital storytelling; narrative: young providers of NBS - bring nature to the table of co-governance/agency of nature itself) 	
Serious games	GPS territorial roadmap (with virtual interface - LKL) of different models (examples) of co-creation and co-governance NBS		Aimed at young people, 13-16 years old; narrative: community building => activation of community resources in a synergistic logic/ community appropriation of solutions in a balance between societal challenges and strengthening of biodiversity
	In Naturebasedpoly, teams collaboratively navigate challenges and assign diverse NBS typologies (Participatory, Territorial, Technological, and Social Solidarity) to specific locations for implementing a comprehensive set of solutions. Players collect resources and navigate challenges through engaging and educational experiences where teams collaboratively assign diverse NBS typologies (Participatory, Territorial, Technological, and Social Solidarity) to specific locations. Players collect resources and navigate challenges, with the ultimate goal of implementing a comprehensive set of solutions. This game serves as a dynamic tool to encourage understanding and discussion around the practical application and benefits of nature-based solutions in real-world contexts, emphasizing cooperation for environmental benefit.		

Table 21: Roadmaps and tools for dissemination and replication of co-governance

Work Package 4 communications status report & evaluation (M1-M30):

The comprehensive governance framework for NBS co-creation (T4.1, D4.1) has been communicated and supported the development of innovative governance strategies tailored for the pilot cases (T4.2, D4.2; and T4.3, D4.3). These insights are now informing multiple areas of the project, including the implementation plans for the eight pilot cases and the ongoing refinement of participatory methods. As the project moves forward, the governance framework will continue to support the monitoring of participatory processes, with lessons learned shaping future dissemination and replication strategies. WP4 has been successful in translating complex governance concepts into practical communication for the pilots. Moreover, WP4, in collaboration with WP6, has developed serious games. The first is a board game available in both English and Portuguese, with plans for translation into additional local languages. The second is a collection of interactive and informative NBS cards, also in English and Portuguese, which will also be translated into more local languages. During Pr3, lessons learned from the implementation of co-governance strategies will inform roadmaps for co-governance taking the form of policy briefs and videos (T4.4). WP4 has also launched educational outreach tailored to local contexts and target audiences, with active youth engagement already underway and NBS concepts being introduced into school curricula.

> Work Package 3: democracy labs as interfaces between science and policies

Local Democracy Labs complement the Living Knowledges Labs by providing a space for elected representatives in the TRANS-lighthouses pilot cases to explore the *what, how and why* of participatory governance of NBS.

What is participatory governance, how can it work in my existing policy environment, how do I get peers on board with the idea, and what elements of these lighthouses are important for us who govern a pilot to know?

The process began with a political round-table, where common dilemmas were identified. These were further refined through bilateral dialogues and the mapping of participatory cultures (T4.2), and then addressed in six Local Democracy Labs with pilot municipalities. In these Labs, elected representatives engaged directly with researchers and practitioners identified from ICLD's wider network to discuss strategies for co-creation, stakeholder engagement, and institutional anchoring of NBS. Insights were consolidated and tested in peer-learning workshops at consortium meetings, where representatives exchanged lessons across sites and identified concrete steps for embedding co-governance in municipal routines.

The iterative sequence of round-table, bilateral exchanges, Local Democracy Labs, and peer-learning workshops inform four policy briefs, five learning cases, and two animated videos. These outputs document political dilemmas, translate research into governance tools, and strengthen the anchoring of NBS in democratic institutions by positioning elected representatives as co-producers of learning. Rather than outlining step-by-step solutions, the learning cases illustrate how a municipality navigated a specific dilemma, what reasoning informed their choices, and what institutional tensions or openings they encountered.

Figure 9: Visualisation of the knowledge flow between research and practice in task 3.6

Work Package 3 communications status report & evaluation (M1-M30):

Significant efforts have been made to transfer knowledge between Work Packages, with a strong focus on supporting the pilot cases. Communication outputs so far include the drafting of Policy Brief 1 and of 4 learning cases, building on Labs and deliverables from other tasks in WP 3 and 4, outlining Policy Briefs 2-4, finalizing the first animated video on community engagement in NBS governance, and drafting the second. The video has been screened and discussed with elected representatives in the pilot cases as well as with local governments and local government associations in ICLD's wider network, including a high-level conference on youth inclusion in Zambia. Dissemination and peer learning opportunities are planned for the upcoming months, both with TRL consortium and with associated partners and ICLD's network of local governments and scholars in ICLD's webinar series Local Democracy Talks and biannual conference Local Democracy Academy. WP3 has played a key role in communicating foundational knowledge and early policy insights.

> Work package 2: co-dissemination of living knowledge

In the framework of Task 2.6 “Co-dissemination of living knowledge”, the deliverable D2.6 “Guidelines for participatory and inclusive knowledge co-dissemination” focuses on providing guidelines about practices and methods of inclusive and participatory knowledge co-dissemination in NBS co-creation. It aims to provide theory- and practice-oriented guidelines that can guide and inspire the pilot cases developed within the project to engage in processes of knowledge co-creation and co-dissemination with citizens and communities.

Traditional forms of academic knowledge dissemination such as journal articles, books and conferences can often fail to reach the target audiences which are the most affected by the project findings. TRANS-lighthouses project has a particular focus on knowledge co-creation and anchoring NBS in local communities aiming for developing citizen-driven nature-based solutions. Therefore, the deliverable D2.6 focuses on ways to build inclusive and participatory knowledge co-dissemination strategies, working with diverse target groups.

The deliverable distinguishes two interrelated types and objectives of co-dissemination:

- Firstly, inclusive dissemination aimed at making knowledge sharing accessible to diverse groups, stakeholders and beneficiaries.
- Secondly, knowledge co-dissemination is approached as a part of broader knowledge co-creation, where citizens play an integral role in co-defining project objectives, research questions and research design, and co-own the knowledge produced in the project.

These objectives are not mutually exclusive, and both of them play an important role in the project timeline. Hence, this deliverable provides guidance on how to work with these interrelated objectives.

The deliverable provides:

i) Discussion of key themes which need to be taken into account in inclusive and participatory knowledge co-dissemination, including

- *Epistemologies of co-production and co-dissemination.* Who creates knowledge and how? (Power relations and epistemological issues in knowledge co-production in Living Knowledge Labs)
- *Collaboration management:* transparency and reflexivity (Transparency about ownership, authorship and joint effort in knowledge co-production and co-dissemination in Living Knowledge Labs)
- *Ethics, risks and consent in co-produced research* (Participatory research involves an often-inherent contradiction between confidentiality and consent due to the dual roles of being participants and co-researchers)

ii) Examples of good practices of inclusive and participatory co-dissemination based on case descriptions

iii) Examples of methods for knowledge co-dissemination

iv) Guidelines and actionable questions to facilitate operationalization of co-dissemination processes in the pilot cases.

Work Package 2 communications status report & evaluation (M1-M30):

Conceptual frameworks on inclusive NBS, unlearning, and human–nature relations have been developed under WP2 and integrated into other Work Packages. Their broad adoption across the project reflects successful internal dissemination and alignment. On this basis work on wider scientific dissemination has now begun as part of the project dissemination strategy, with future outputs expected to share these insights with the broader academic community.

2.4.4. Events and publication channels

> Schedule and selection of past and planned consortium events

General schedule of consortium meetings and events					
	In-person consortium meetings	Online consortium meetings	Periodic reviews	Technical visits	Conferences
2023	CM #1 - M2 21-23 June 2023 Azores				
		CM#2 - M6 24-25 Oct 2023			
2024	CM #3 - M10 28 Feb - 1 Mar. 2024 Rome			Brussels - M21	
		CM #4 - M14 June 2024			
	CM #5 - M18 Oct. 2024 Cáceres		PR1 - M18-M2 Oct./Dec. 2024		
2025		CM #6 - M21 Jan. 2025		Brussels - M21	
	CM #7 - M25 May -2025 Estarreja/ Barcelos				
		CM #8 - M29 Oct. 2025			
			PR2 - M30-M32 Oct./Dec. 2025	Madrid - M31	
2026	CM #9 - M33 Feb. 2026 Strovolos			Upper Allgau Zealand	Winter school - M33 Strovolos
					School/Conf. - M37 May 2026 Brussels
		CM #10 - M41 Sep. 2026			
			Final review		

Table 22: General schedule of consortium meetings and events, year 2 updated version.

Selection/mapping of events	
Types of events	Types of involvement
EU / European Commission events	Application/Invitation for public communications/exhibitions/workshops <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Europe Day - New European Bauhaus Festival - European week of regions and cities - Innovation days
Networking events organised by relevant associations	Application/Invitation for public communications/exhibitions/workshops <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ENoLL - JPI Urban Europe - DUT - Social Economy European Forum - Gathering of the Global Ecovillage Network of Europe (GEN Europe) - Congreso Nacional del Medio Ambiente de España e Iberoamérica CONAMA 2024 - Encuentro de Pueblos y Ciudades por la Sostenibilidad de España CONAMA LOCAL 2025 - New European Bauhaus https://neweuropeanbauhaus.es/en/ - EUGREEN, European Universities Alliance for Sustainability: responsible GRowth, inclusive Education and Environment - 13er Congreso de Compostaje Descentralizado de Composta En Red (Octubre 2024) - "XV Congreso SEAE Producción Ecológica, compartida con nuestra tierra, gente y alimentos" (Abril 2024) - 39ª edición Biocultura Madrid y 30ª edición Biocultura Barcelona - ENANPARQ 2024 - Encontro da Associação Nacional de Pesquisa e Pós-graduação em Arquitetura e Urbanismo - EUROELECS 2025 - Encontro Latino-americano e Europeu sobre Edificações e Comunidades Sustentáveis

International and referenced conferences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Application/Invitation for public communications - ISA World Congress of Sociology - EURA Conference - NESS - Degrowth - IUFRO - ECSWR 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 19th European Congress of Psychology (https://ecp2025.eu/) - World Urban Forum - COP16 Biodiversity 2024 (Colombia) - 2024 Ocean Decade Conference (Barcelona) - COP29 - Baku - COP30 - Brazil
Webinars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organisation of internal and/or open webinars: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - presentations of horizontal partners and discussions with the consortium members, associated partners and invited participants - dissemination and appropriation of ethics principles, guidelines, procedures and requirements by partners - meetings with ethics board - Webinar Series: NBS, yes? Under what conditions? (TRL - Task force on Community Economies, Transformative Economies and NBS) 	
Clustering initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Joint events with sibling projects COEVOLVERS and NATURESCAPES - NBS Task Forces gathering EU funded projects - Joint events with sibling project EUGREEN - REAL DEAL https://www.realdeal.eu/about 	
Local community events of scientific knowledge dissemination	Organised as part of the Living Knowledge Labs activities, in the framework of consortium meetings and technical visits to the sites of the pilot cases	
Local dissemination and training workshops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dissemination of research and guidelines to amplify the involvement of youth and older adults in the co-creation of NBS - In connection with the community-driven communication process based on youth protagonism, and the digital platform of task 6.4, to disseminate more broadly research results, guidelines and activities developed with youth 	
Democracy labs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Space for local government officers and politicians to meet researchers (task 3.6) - Roundtables with elected representatives 	

Table 23: Selection/mapping of events

> Selection of publication channels

Mapping of publication opportunities	
Types of publication	Selection of publications/media
> Open research platforms	- Horizon Results Platform
> Open access publications	- Global Environmental Change (Elsevier)
> International referenced publications (scientific, technical, architect, environmental journals)	- Environment and Behavior (Sage)
	- Environment and Planning A (Sage)
	- Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment (Elsevier)
	- Nature-based solutions (Elsevier)
> Publications with processing charge/fee afforded by the project to grant free access to readers	- Environmental Monitoring and Assessment (Springer)
	- Environment and Planning D: Society and Space (Sage)
	- Critical Reviews in Environmental Science and Technology (Taylor & Francis)
	- Psychosocial Intervention (JCR (Q1), IF 4.8)
	- Social Inclusion (JCR, IF 1.5)
	- Arquitecturas del Sur
	- Revista Nacional de Gerenciamiento de Ciudades
	- Periódico Técnico e Científico Ciudades Verdes
> Specialised magazines/journals	- Centro de Publicaciones del Ministerio para la Transición Ecológica y el Reto Demográfico (Spain)
> Specialised blogs and forums	- TED Talks and TED X Talks
>> Featured project presentations	- Partners' pages in local media: Jornal Açoriano Oriental / Page Movimento Kairós
> General media	
>> Media appearances (i.e. TV, radio)	
>> Featured in local media	

Table 24: Mapping of publication opportunities

Status report & evaluation of events & publication channels (M1-M30):

To track and manage events and publications there are 4 essential tools:

Event Management

To streamline event management, we utilize two distinct yet complementary spreadsheets:

1. **"Events Attendance Planning"**: This spreadsheet serves as a comprehensive repository for all external scientific dissemination and stakeholder engagement events. It is regularly updated to include both pre-identified and newly discovered opportunities, capturing key details like dates and deadlines.
2. **"Dissemination and Communication Tracking"**: This dynamic spreadsheet monitors all communication, dissemination, and exploitation (CDE) activities from project partners, including our participation in the events listed above. The data from this tool is continuously updated and used for technical reporting (see section 3.4 monitoring tools for more details).

Publication Management

Similarly to event management, there are two distinct, complementary spreadsheets used to streamline publication management:

1. **"Mapping of Publication Opportunities"**: This document provides a detailed overview of potential publication channels. The initial list has been refined to include crucial details such as cost, journal ranking, and indexing to guide our selection process.
2. **"Central Management Tool for Publications"**: This spreadsheet organizes publication opportunities that arise directly from the project's work, categorized by dissemination type and corresponding deliverable.

See Appendix 1 for screenshots of each management tool.

2.4.5. Digital strategy

> Internal communication platform and cloud

In their daily collaborative work, the consortium members make use of online tools and platforms for project management and team communication that are the most commonly used and accessible among partners, in compliance with the data management requirements. Partners are also equipped in their institutions with communications tools that allow online interactions and collaborative work, such as video conferencing.

- Communication and project management platform: Basecamp

Basecamp is a web-based project management and collaboration tool. It provides partners with:

- centralised platform for organising tasks and sharing files;
- centralised communication (reducing the need for scattered emails and improving transparency within projects);
- user-friendly interface (use without extensive training).

- Cloud: Google drive

As established in the data management plan (v1, deliverable D1.2), data collected/generated is stored to Google Drive cloud servers using a commercial, non-public licence of Google Workspace that meets privacy and security requirements to comply with the General Data Protection Regulation ([GDPR](#)). It provides partners with:

- unified and real-time collaboration platform: teams can collaborate on documents, spreadsheets, and presentations in real-time;
- file accessibility: from anywhere with an internet connection; offline access also available;

- version control features help track changes and revision;
- centralised administration over user accounts, permissions, and security settings.

- File findability and accessibility: Naming convention

As specified in the data management plan (v1, deliverable D1.2), a file naming convention has been agreed and established for all files generated throughout the project. This naming convention defines the rules and abbreviations used for naming and identifying files, thus facilitating their findability and accessibility.

More precisely, the established convention includes the following sequence of components, using underscore as a delimiter between them:

1. Project abbreviation, namely TRL.
2. Work package number, e.g. WP1.
3. Data provider (partner), e.g. ARC, RUC.
4. File type:
 - DATA for data files, datasets,
 - SW for software,
 - DX.Y for deliverables, as indicated in the grant agreement (where X, Y arithmetic parameters),
 - PLT-XXX for pilots, where XXX is the abbreviation of the pilot case,
 - ASSC-XXX for assessment cases, where XXX is the abbreviation of the assessment case.
5. Date [YYYYMM].
6. Title/description (short free text).
7. Version vXY (where X, Y arithmetic parameters).

Internal communication status & progress report:

The established digital infrastructure, which includes Basecamp for project management, Google Drive for cloud storage, and a strict file naming convention, remains fully operational and in active use by all partners.

Basecamp continues to serve as the central hub for all project-related tasks, file sharing, and communication, successfully reducing email traffic and enhancing transparency among partners.

Google Drive remains the project's secure cloud storage solution. The centralized administration of Google Workspace guarantees that all privacy and security requirements are met.

The file naming system is being consistently applied to all project files. This standardized approach has been crucial in maintaining an organized file structure that ensures that all documents are easily findable and accessible to the consortium members.

> Public repository: Zenodo

As established in the data management plan (v1, deliverable D1.2), deliverables and research results of the project classified as public (i.e. unless restricted by [GDPR](#) or deliverables considered confidential), as well as all scientific publications deriving from it, were made publicly available with open access:

- at the project's website, and/or
- in the Zenodo trustworthy open repository through the TRANS-lighthouses community³, under the supported Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International licence, in addition to the European Commission Funded Research (OpenAIRE) Community⁴.

> Website

- Domain and hosting

www.trans-lighthouses.eu is the domain registered by CES-UC.

- It includes a hyphen for readability.
- Hosting is guaranteed by CES-UC until 2 years after the end of the project.
- Secure Sockets Layer (SSL) certificate was purchased by CES-UC for the address www.trans-lighthouses.eu in order to encrypt communications between the server and visitors.

³ <https://zenodo.org/communities/trans-lighthouses/>

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/communities/openaire/>

- Development stages

a communication agency was hired to develop the website (FBA. - Ferrand, Bicker & Associados, www.fba.pt)

- 4-stage development according to project advancements and needs.

Stabe 1 Until month 8 Dec. 2023	Stage 2 Until month 18 Oct. 2024	Stage 3 Until month 30 Oct. 2025	Stage 4 Until month 42 Oct. 2026	
Inclusion of basic structure and contents	Complement structure and contents	Complement structure and contents	Adapt structure and contents for the closing of the project	
Beginning of the project	Middle of the project	Middle of the project	End of the project	2 years after end of project
Communication				
	Dissemination			
		Exploitation		

Figure 10: Website - 4-stage development

- Contents development and management

- Contents are collaboratively developed by the partners of the project TRANS-lighthouses.
- The website is available in English.
- Communication in the local language of partners and stakeholders from different countries is applicable in the framework of the Living Knowledge Labs of pilot cases and community-based communication, i.e. digital platform and other Educommunication channels, materials and tools developed with Jangada, as part of work package 6.
- Content management system (CMS) provides us with autonomy to maintain and update contents.
- Back office system enables to create profiles for transversal management of the website's content, i.e. system administrators.
- System administrators can create, delete and edit other back office users with the possibility of defining different access permissions.
- In addition to the definition of roles and contributions among consortium members, we have been equipped with two training sessions on the use of back office and guidelines on good practices in editing/introducing content.

- Structure and functioning⁵

Website main structure/menu - Header					
About	Partners	Lighthouses	News and events	Resources and tools	Contact us
> Objectives & methodology > Work plan > Inspiration	> Consortium > Associated partners > Ethics commission > Gender Equality and Diversity focal point > Sibling projects	> Interactive map > Assessment cases >> Specific pages > Pilot cases >> Specific pages	> News > Calendar > Press room	> Research and innovation > Citizen science > Public repository > Democracy labs > Community-driven communication	Contact information, newsletter signup, social media

Table 25: Website main structure/menu - Header

Additional features and functionalities

- Privacy policy: clearly communicate the website's privacy policy and data handling practices, quality and GDPR Policy; cookies disclaimer.
- Measures to protect sensitive project data and user information
- Search functionality

⁵ Details on the technical functioning and development of the project website—including its features and specifications across sections and subsections—are thoroughly outlined in Table 24 of Deliverable 1.1. This document is available for download under the Resources section of the TRANS-lighthouses website. As the website is now live and fully operational, extensive technical descriptions are not repeated here. For a complete overview of the website's architecture and functionalities, please refer to Deliverable 1.1 or explore the website directly.

- Data visualisation
- Restricted access to some resources
- Accessibility: adoption of web content accessibility guidelines
- User analytics
- Mobile responsiveness
- Feedback mechanism
- Green web hosting: adoption of green web hosting practices

> Social media

The choice of social media platforms has depended on the project's goals, target audiences, communication strategy and capability. A social media strategy was created at the beginning of the project, considering also:

- who and how frequently the chosen platforms will be updated;
- unlike the website that serves as a business card and explanation, social media platforms typically require constant updates and investment, some more than others;
- to create and post relevant and adequate/professional contents (visuals and messaging);
- to prepare and implement rigorous and efficient planning for posts, elaboration/design of contents;
- to allocate budget for paid advertising or sponsored content;
- to monitor and moderate interactions;
- content curation;
- compliance with data protection, as well as in terms of intellectual property and data ownership;
- to report regularly on the impact of posts, the evolution of the audience of our social media account/profile, and other social media metrics;
- local groups engaged in the Living Knowledge Labs of pilots may also develop their local social media pages, which will be managed autonomously by them, and may also relay our messages/posts;
- we may also rely on the pages of partners and their institutions.

An assessment was conducted at the start of the project to guide the choice of which social media platform to invest our efforts in. Firstly by mapping possible social media platforms, and, secondly by considering both advantages/benefits and challenges in use and maintenance. This initial assessment has been continuously evaluated throughout the project.

Assessment for social media strategy and content plan		
Platforms	Decision	Justification
> LinkedIn > Padlet > YouTube	Suitable	- Appropriate target audiences - Manageable - Available resources for investment
> ResearchGate > Academia.edu > EurekAlert! > ScienceDaily > The Conversation > SciDev.Net	Needing further assessment	Further assess: - relevance - our management capacity - available resources for investment
> Facebook > X (Twitter) > SlideShare > Instagram	Not suitable	- No added value - Heavy management and resources needed - Overlapping community-driven communication

Table 26: Assessment for social media strategy and content plan

Public repository, website and social media status & progress report:

The TRANS-lighthouses website continues to be a cornerstone of the project's dissemination strategy, functioning effectively as the central hub for all project information. Developed in collaboration between FBA and project management and published between M17-M18, the site is operating smoothly and is kept current

through continuous updates managed by the Project Manager. The established workflow for content management remains efficient. LinkedIn is the most actively used social media platform, consistently publishing 2-4 posts per month. This significantly surpasses the initial goal of one post per month, indicating strong and consistent engagement on this channel. YouTube activity is present but lower. The creation of video content is resource and knowledge-intensive, which contributes to the lower volume of posts on this platform. The use of Padlet has declined since its initiation. As it is not centrally managed, encouragement and reminders are needed to boost its utilization among partners.

Partners contribute content through a collaborative spreadsheet "LinkedIn&Youtube (SoMe), Website & Newsletter Requests", which is then reviewed to ensure quality and compliance with project standards. In this spreadsheet partners can submit proposals for content across the various platforms and channels. This system is functioning effectively, guarantees a streamlined and organized approach to generating and publishing of content across platforms. Partners This process ensures a steady flow of relevant and engaging updates.

Performance across social media and communication platforms is monitored every 90 days. These data-driven insights have guided continuous evaluation and optimization of the content. This ensures the social media channels and websites effectively serves its purpose of disseminating project outcomes to a diverse audience.

Monitoring across central communication platforms;

Newsletter	LinkedIn	Website	Youtube
Mailchimp Analytics	LinkedIn Analytics	Google Analytics	Youtube Analytics / manual

Analytics from central communication platforms

(The analytics represent the previous 90 days for M22, M25, M28 and the previous 60 days for M30)

Month	Newsletter	LinkedIn	Webpage	Youtube
M22 Feb-25	<u>Newsletter #1:</u> Subscribers 52 Unsubscribed 0 Open rate 68.6%	Impressions 3,280 -23.3% Page views 60 +215.8% New followers 32 -34.7%	Total users 101 +13.5% New users +1.3% Views 389 -12.2%	Subscribers 8 +/- 0 Impressions 356 Views 7
M25 May-25		Impressions 2,618 -36.6% Comments 10 +233.3% Page views 22 -6.9% New followers 22 -33.3%	Total users 283 +18.4% New users 252 +16.7% Views 1.4K +12.5%	Subscribers 36 +350% Impressions 327 -8.15% Views 41 +485%
M28 Aug-25	<u>Newsletter #2</u> Subscribers 72 +18.0% Unsubscribed 0 Open rate 54.7%	Impressions 2,618 -36.6% Comments 10 +233.3% Page views 22 -6.9% New followers 18 -18.2%	Total users 769 +180.7% New users 739 +206.6% Views 2.2K +57.9%	Subscribers 39 +8% Impressions 239 -26.91% Views 69 +68%
M30 Oct-25	No new newsletter sent the previous analytics	Impressions 2,977 +675.3% Comments 8 +166.7% Page views 78 +169% New followers 23 +283.3%	Total users 206 +34.6% New users 184 +41.5% Views 899 +14.4%	Subscribers 40 +2.5% Impressions 44 Views 14

Monitoring across Community platforms;

Website	Articles	Instagram
Google Analytics	Manual	Manual

Analytics from Community platforms

(The analytics represent the previous 90 days for M22, M25, M28 and the previous 60 days for M30)

Month	Nr. website visits	Nr. of articles published	Nr. of Instagram posts
M22 Feb-25	383	12	27
M25 May-25	465	18	20
M28 Aug-25	365	16	18
M30 Oct-25			
TOTAL	1364	78	82

2.5. Awareness raising, development and implementation of guidelines

> Images and messaging

- Build upon existing ethical content guidelines

Updated version of [The Dóchas Code of Conduct on Images and Messages \(2006\)](#) and [The Illustrative Guide to the Dóchas Code of Conduct on Images and Messages \(2014\)](#)

Figure 11: Dóchas Guide to Ethical Communications 2023
Source: (Dóchas, 2023)

- Core values and commitments

Images and messaging: core values and commitments		
Core values	Meaning	Commitments
Respect for the dignity of people concerned	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > appreciating the people and situations > showing consideration for people's privacy and dignity > regarding people as active, valuable and capable agents of change in their own lives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >> Authentic representation: providing truth and context when portraying the lives of individuals and communities >> Contributor-led stories and locally led content development: putting the people and communities at the centre of communications
Belief in the equality of all people	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > respecting the rights of all people > applying the same standards to everyone > promoting an appreciation of diversity > committing to non-discrimination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >> Informed consent: all content is obtained with the full understanding, participation and permission of those featured, or in the case of children, of their parents or guardians
Acceptance of the need to promote solidarity, fairness and justice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > <i>Solidarity:</i> using practices, images and messages that promote working together with, rather than on behalf, of communities. > <i>Fairness and justice:</i> highlighting causes, calling for actions to address them and implementing a rights-based approach 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >> Upholding standards and Doing No Harm In planning, gathering and disseminating content <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - conform to the highest standards and international instruments relating to human rights - commit to the protection of people in vulnerable situations and those with specific needs

Table 27: Images and messaging: core values and commitments
Adapted from Dóchas Guide to Ethical Communications 2023

> Gender

- Gender responsiveness: An integrated approach

The TRANS-lighthouses' Gender+ dimension ("plus") refers to the gender inclusivity perspective, considering non-binary persons as a result of the LGBTIQA+ struggles (Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, Intersex, Queer, Asexual, + any other), as well as the complex combination of different oppressions and discriminations.

Voice, participation, engagement, accountability and rights regarding gender are key aspects to be taken into account during the project implementation. It is not an "add on" to project work but rather a central aspect that was considered since TRANS-lighthouses' conception.

The consortium proposal has largely involved female researchers and holds a prominent position in leading, managing and coordinating the project. We continuously aim for a gender balance throughout the consortium, including the local teams from pilot cases, and throughout the participants in the Living Knowledge(s) Labs.

The project strives for gender equality in the consortium, echoing the growing attention and measures to push gender balance in projects funded by the European Commission. Annexe 5 of our Grant Agreement includes specific rules, namely:

- Art. 14 on gender mainstreaming which states that: *"The beneficiaries must take all measures to promote equal opportunities between men and women in the implementation of the action and, where applicable, in line with the gender equality plan. They must aim, to the extent possible, for a gender balance at all levels of personnel assigned to the action, including at supervisory and managerial level"*.
- Art. 18 on carrying out the action and addressing access to research infrastructure activities, stating that the beneficiaries must *"promote equal opportunities in advertising the access and take into account the gender dimension when defining the support provided to users"*.

In the initial D1.1 CDE plan, a gender assessment framework for events was developed, based around six main topics, to be monitored before, during, and after events;

Assessment framework - Gender																																																	
1 Gender balance in the composition of sessions coordination, presenters and participants - Balance of women/men (organising/invited, attending) - Balance in terms of positions (senior men/women, junior men/women)	Template of online post-event survey - Gender I. To what extent did the event fulfil the following objectives in relation to gender <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>1</th> <th>2</th> <th>3</th> <th>4</th> <th>5</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>- Openness for all genders to submit contributions to the program</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>- Balanced representation of genders among the participants of the event</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>- Representative coverage in the programme of sessions of different gender issues in relation to nature-based solutions for inclusive communities</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>- Discussions during main and parallel sessions inclusive for all genders</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>- Balanced representation of genders amongst session coordinators/reporteurs</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>- New insights were presented concerning gender aspect in relation to citizen engagement in nature-based solutions</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>- Overall, the event was an equal opportunity for all genders to participate and contribute</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		1	2	3	4	5	- Openness for all genders to submit contributions to the program						- Balanced representation of genders among the participants of the event						- Representative coverage in the programme of sessions of different gender issues in relation to nature-based solutions for inclusive communities						- Discussions during main and parallel sessions inclusive for all genders						- Balanced representation of genders amongst session coordinators/reporteurs						- New insights were presented concerning gender aspect in relation to citizen engagement in nature-based solutions						- Overall, the event was an equal opportunity for all genders to participate and contribute					
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- Overall, the event was an equal opportunity for all genders to participate and contribute																																																	
2 Composition of topics and entrees - Relevance of the topics to the lives of women and men - Illustrations and photos in the materials	II. Your experiences around gender issues at the event <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th></th> <th>1</th> <th>2</th> <th>3</th> <th>4</th> <th>5</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>- I experienced concrete examples of gender discrimination</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>- I observed gender bias in one or more of the presentations</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>- I enjoyed specific participant contributions that unprogrammed highlighted important gender issue</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		1	2	3	4	5	- I experienced concrete examples of gender discrimination						- I observed gender bias in one or more of the presentations						- I enjoyed specific participant contributions that unprogrammed highlighted important gender issue																													
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- I experienced concrete examples of gender discrimination																																																	
- I observed gender bias in one or more of the presentations																																																	
- I enjoyed specific participant contributions that unprogrammed highlighted important gender issue																																																	
3 Accessibility - Safe travelling to the event venue - Disability-accessible toilet facilities - Separate toilet for men and women - Prayer spaces - Child care - Timing according to parents responsibilities - Affordability/funding for participation	1. Not at all; 2. To a low extent; 3. To a medium extent; 4. To a high extent; 5. Don't know																																																
4 Management and composition - Monitoring gender responsiveness in preparation and delivery stages - Making clear that women and men are welcome - Gender neutral language																																																	
5 Facilitation, moderation, chair and note-taking of sessions - Balance of women/men invited - Gender awareness and responsiveness																																																	
6 Monitoring & evaluation - Survey gender of participants; relevance of the presentations and discussions for gender diversity; according to gender ID, assess if the needs and expectations of men/women/other genders were met; evaluation of gender sensitiveness of the event in terms of equal opportunities to present/talk/discuss; suitability of the event in terms of adequate facilities, friendly communication and support for different genders - Mechanism to replicate lessons learned regarding gender responsiveness by the partners' organisations - Compilation of gender-related issues: that were raised during discussions and that arose during organisation or running of event																																																	

Snapshots of initial Gender Assessment Frameworks.
(For full checklists, see D.1.1).

Figure 12: Initial gender assessment framework

Through the experience in the project so far and our assessments emerging from our work together we have assessed that gender responsiveness is a foundational principle woven throughout the TRANS-lighthouses project, that needs to extend beyond mere participation metrics to actively integrate gender perspectives in all phases, from partner engagement to knowledge co-creation. This section outlines some crucial aspects of the project's comprehensive approach to ensuring gender equity and inclusivity.

TRANS-lighthouses incorporates a **gender analysis throughout the project:**

- within the development of co-creation tools (WP2 and 6);
- in the assessment of the co-creation (WP3), in the implementation of the pilot cases (WP5);
- as well as co-governance approaches (WP4).

Gender dimension and diversity is emphasised through a range of theoretical, methodological and technical approaches used in the research. Thus, a transnational and multi-scale perspective in itself implies problematizing identities and geographies.

>Gender focal points

To ensure that gender equality takes priority in all aspects of the project, TRANS-lighthouses has appointed a Gender Equality and Diversity (GED) focal point, as devised in task 1.1 and in articulation with task 2.5 with the responsibility of monitoring and ensuring that the project is inclusive, equitable and diverse in the management of its consortium and in its approach and interventions in the project implementation.

> Inclusive partner engagement

We continuously promote the participation of diverse gender perspectives within our consortium and among external stakeholders. This involves targeted outreach and creating inclusive environments for collaboration and dialogue.

> Monitoring using social dimension indicators

The project utilizes specific social indicators, including the gender aspect, to monitor and evaluate the impact of our activities. These indicators track not only the presence of women but also their meaningful involvement, influence on decision-making, and the extent to which project outcomes address gender-specific needs and challenges.

> Ethical considerations in participatory activities

Guided by Work Package 6's commitment to citizen science, we integrate ethical considerations of socio-political factors into all participatory activities within the Local Knowledge Labs (LKLs). This ensures that the voices and needs of women and other traditionally underrepresented social specificities are actively sought, respected, and incorporated, thereby continuously striving for inclusive and equitable co-creation processes and outcomes. (For more information consolidate Deliverable 6.8).

> Integration of women's knowledge

We prioritize the inclusion of women's unique knowledge, experiences, and perspectives in all research, development, and dissemination activities. This ensures that solutions are contextually relevant and address the diverse realities of all community members.

> **Capacity building**

Training and awareness-raising initiatives are conducted to enhance gender sensitivity among project partners and stakeholders, fostering a deeper understanding of gender issues and their relevance to nature-based solutions.

- **Gender-sensitive communication and gender-responsive approach**

Gender-sensitive communication

Communication levels and function: interpersonal, institutional, science
Source: [SUPERA project](#)

Ensuring visibility to all the components of the research and academia community
Source: [SUPERA project](#)

5 areas of gender-sensitive communication
Source: [SUPERA project](#)

Key aspects	Resources
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Importance of having a gender perspective, even in communication activities and in the construction of an imaginary. > Sometimes implicit choices, but not so obvious. > Images with both men and women, boys and girls. > Pictures that do not reinforce stereotypes. > Mention both men and women in all discourses. > Big responsibility for those involved in communication. > Reflect on how to communicate the project, representing women and girls. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Horizon 2020 project SUPERA: Guidelines for gender-sensitive communication in research and academia > Guides for non sexist language used in institutions of the consortium > European Institute for Gender Equality: Toolkit on Gender-sensitive Communication

Table 28: Gender-sensitive communication

Gender-responsive approach in events

Created by Jooyun Lee from Noun Project

Created by Jooyun Lee from Noun Project

Created by Srivivas Agra from Noun Project

Diversity promoted and welcome	International recommendations to coordinators/moderators	International recommendations to presenters
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Making clear that women and men are welcome: "Men and women and broader gender diversity are promoted and welcome"; "if you need any help, clarification or would like to report or give suggestions". > Gender neutral language in the conference website and communication materials 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Equal chances to ask questions > Challenge gender stereotypes or prejudice > Note of gender-related issues > Inform about online survey 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Clarify the relevance of gender balance in relation to the topic presented > Illustrations and photos that reflect and value the experience of women/girls and men/boys > Information about online survey

Topics and recommendations: partially adapted from ["Topics and Organizing gender-responsive trainings and meetings"](#) - UNESCO Bangkok Office

Table 29: Gender-responsive approach in events and presentations

Evaluation and status report of gender framework

The project's approach to gender integration has been significantly broader and more comprehensive than what was initially captured by the D1.1 Gender checklists. The original gender framework proved to be too narrow to encompass the full spectrum of gender-related activities and experiences within the consortium and events. Instead of relying solely on the checklist, the project has adopted a more dynamic approach, where gender is incorporated throughout the consortium and the work in each Work Package. A key aspect of the gender assessment is the ethical focal points that have been established in each LKL. The focal points have a number of different checklists to guide activities, preparation, and observation.

During the fifth consortium meeting, two activities were organized to address gender-related issues within the consortium. The first activity involved an anonymous "gender box" where female members could share their personal experiences with gender issues. These submissions were then used as the basis for a "gender icebreaker" activity. During the icebreaker, statements derived from the submissions were read aloud. Participants who had not experienced the situation described in the statement took a step forward, while those who had remained in place. The exercise was highly successful and proved to be a powerful eye-opener for many attendees.

During the 6th consortium a workshop was fully dedicated to gender issues in the consortium, project management and within each Work Package. For gender and PM, three working groups were established for 1. Publications, 2. Communication, and 3. Dissemination materials and documents. Each working group created a set of recommendations with related actionable steps.

> Sustainability

Trying to start on the right foot was a concern to design and organise the first in-person collective meeting based on the principles of sustainability and the circular economy. We consider the practices adopted in the kick-off event of TRANS-lighthouses not as a final product or even a recipe, but rather as a foundation from which to build something better.

- Sustainable events

Keeping in mind the principles of sustainability and the circular economy some measures have been adopted, such as:

Measures based on the principles of sustainability and the circular economy

- > Promotion of the event mainly through the media, digital marketing and social networks (local and transnational)
- > Programme of the event, partly in hybrid format
- > Raising awareness on good environmental practices among partners
- > Performance indicators that are continuously refined and evaluated throughout the project (social, economic and environmental impacts)
- > Use of pre-existing facilities
- > Use of the regular installations/equipment, such as canteen of the university (energy reduction)
- > Lunch outdoors (energy reduction)
- > Purchase in social and solidarity companies that provide local/regional products and traditional gastronomy
- > Print content to be reused in all events (specifically, one roll-up to be used in other meetings)
- > Use of digital documents and materials (e.g. invitation letters and certificates of attendance)
- > Less/no goodies, recycled materials and local readable gifts
- > Waste collection / recycling (glass-plastic-paper and biowaste)
- > Adoption of reusable products and packing in the coffee-break services

- > Offer to solidarity institutions the food and materials not used
- > Minimise carbon emission on routes/activities during the days of the event, by favouring walking and using collective transport for activities

Table 30: Organisation of events: measures based on the principles of sustainability and the circular economy

-Checklist for sustainable events

In the first CDE plan (D1.1), an initial framework for sustainability was presented as well, with the intent to be tested and fine-tuned based on monitoring before, during, and after events. This framework was designed to be enriched with recommendations, indicators, and assessments emerging from the project's work.

Assessment framework - Sustainability		
Impact & Indicators	Measurement	Results
I. Environmental impact		
Number of plastic bottles collected	Unity	
Total of reused papers	Kg	
Total of meals repurposed	Kg	
Total bio waste collected	Kg	
Estimation - by foot or cycle distances	Km	
Total of reused glass bottles	Unity	
% of collective buildings used	%	
% of outdoor spaces used	%	
Total of collective transports used (ratio by: number of passengers vs n. of participants) / Car-pooling (ratio by: number of vehicles vs number of passengers).	Unity	
Format adopted to ensure inclusive participation and to reduce travelling	Strategy	
Total of resources dematerialized, including certificates, programmes and others.	Unity	
Total of the disposable utensils used (the goal is zero)	Unity	
Total of gifts and merchandising in recycled material or reusable	Unity	
II. Economic impact		
Expenses incurred with/for local NBS during the event	€	
Total of expenses incurred with local social enterprises	€	
Total of expenses incurred with local companies (small and micro)	€	
III. Social impact		
Number of social enterprises and social projects included in the event	Unity	
Number of students participating in the event implementation (youth engagement)	Number	

Figure 13: Assessment framework - Sustainability

- Green web

The principles of the green web advocate for a mindful approach to digital infrastructure, focusing on low technology, zero waste, and minimal energy consumption to achieve a positive and regenerative impact on nature. These guidelines involve practical considerations, such as being clear in sizing the website according to the capacity and need for energy consumption that is to be saved. This concept extends to managing consumption patterns, such as considering lower consumption at night and higher consumption in the afternoon, similar to the usage times of domestic machines. The focus on digital sustainability is an important aspect of the project's commitment to its overarching sustainability goals. The initial CDE plan comprised the list below to guide the implementation of green web principles in the project.

References for green web

Green Web Hosting Certification Types: the two main types of certifications related to green web hosting are Renewable Energy Certificates (REC) for anyone, and Carbon Offset Certificates (VER) for large companies with a database centre.

Information from the European Union on <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/green-cloud> green guidelines and 'green host':

Information on websites using green host <https://www.thegreenwebfoundation.org> in the world:

Example of web hosted in a green host: <https://store.mosaert.com/ethics/green-web>

Example on low tech activism and website design: <https://solar.lowtechmagazine.com/2023/06/rebuilding-a-solar-powered-website>

Table 31: References for Green Web

Sustainability status report & evaluation:

The implementation of sustainability within the project, similarly to the gender dimension, has been more extensive than anticipated by the initial checklist. It has been recognized that the resources and time demanded for the comprehensive quantitative measurements of the for the initial checklist would significantly outweigh the benefits. Therefore, a more qualitative approach was adopted for assessing sustainability throughout events, prioritizing broader impact and learning outcomes over detailed quantitative metrics. This includes a diverse set of internal, external, and scientific indicators (developed within Task 3.2. & 3.3.). Key areas of promoting green events include prioritizing local food and catering, avoiding single-use items, minimizing excessive travel and air traffic by encouraging public transport, and introducing composting initiatives. These efforts have and continue to serve both a scientific component of the projects as well as an internal learning and awareness-creation process.

The project has integrated green web principles into its own digital infrastructure and has actively promoted these concepts across the consortium. The official project website is hosted at CES-UC, Portugal, which benefits from the University of Coimbra's commitment to renewable energy sources, thereby supporting "green hosting" measures. This ensures that the project's primary digital presence aligns with its sustainability goals from a fundamental infrastructure perspective.

Beyond the project's direct implementation, a key focus has been on capacity building and awareness-raising among partners. During the website development phase, partners were informed about green guidelines and the concept of a 'green host,'.

While the project has been successful in implementing these guidelines for its own website and raised awareness among consortium members, there is a recognized limitation in measuring the broader impact. Since consortium members are often distinct from the institutional teams responsible for managing their respective organizational websites, the project does not have the capacity to monitor or evaluate the adoption of these green web recommendations across partner institutions. The project's success in this area is therefore measured by the level of internal awareness and the successful implementation of green hosting for the project's own digital infrastructure.

> Accessibility

- Meetings, work/family reconciliation, events, web

Not all people participate in the same way or under the same circumstances. Each person is different and has different preferences/styles, abilities, opportunities or restrictions. As a matter of promoting fluid meetings, active listening and accessible participation, TRANS-lighthouses' partners have been exchanging practices and concerns that are explored throughout the project.

Accessible communication and interaction: practices and concerns

Online video conferencing

Created by IconTrack from Noun Project

> Key aspects on Zoom/video conference fatigue:

> Somatic and cognitive exhaustion that is caused by the intensive and/or inappropriate use of videoconferencing tools, frequently accompanied by related symptoms such as tiredness, worry, anxiety, burnout, discomfort, and stress, as well as other bodily symptoms such as headaches (Riedl, 2022).

> Back-to-back video calls: no time for mental, visual, or physical break (while it exists for in-person meetings)

> Other factors contributing to this fatigue: much more eye-to-eye contact than usual; harder to read nonverbal cues and body language; seeing ourselves in the corner of the screen; less mobility/moving around

> Improve interaction on video calls:

>> Plan some extra time at the beginning to check in and then focus on working through the agenda

>> Agenda: prepare, share in advance and follow

>> Avoid multitasking

>> Reduce screen stimuli: turn self view; plain backgrounds; turn your camera off when lot of people or majority of screen-shared presentations; reduce size of video call screen to avoid excessive direct eye-contact

>> Breaks during meetings to re-energise and transition periods between meetings (e.g. get up and stretch your legs, enjoy some fresh air, get some water, coffee, snack, fruit)

>> Whenever possible shorter calls: people positively engaged rather than distracted or uncomfortable

>> Mix of communication methods to limit video calls: shared/collaborative documents; clear brief notes and emails to avoid overload of information; instant messenger/Ping; phone calls instead

Assembly signs

Created by Robinson Moreno from Nour Project

> Key aspects on promoting fluid meetings, active listening and participation:

- > Not all people participate in the same way or under the same circumstances
- > Each person is different and has different preferences/styles, abilities

> Improve communication in meetings and assemblies:

in favour / against / you are extending / you are repeating yourself / you can't be heard well / I don't see it, but I don't block

Source: https://15mpedia.org/wiki/Signos_asamblearios

Work/family reconciliation

Created by Guillermo Appolinario from Nour Project

> Key aspects on work/family reconciliation and participation in events:

- > Raised by partners on the occasion of the first general assembly (23 June 2023)
- > Importance of participation in events to the careers, namely present work, get published, networking opportunities
- > However, there are personal costs for travelling abroad and being away during several days, such as family constraints that need to be rearranged and afforded, missing important moments in the life of family members

> How to make events more inclusive for families?

- to be considered for the preparation of events and consortium meetings;
- survey participants if they might want to bring children and families;
- assess the need for options/measures to be applied case-by-case and to the overall organisation of events;
- e.g. family-friendly locations/destinations with programmes, activities and attractions for children and families; licensed local childcare options; hotels with family suites; participation in one or more social events; arrangements and premises for parenting and caregiving; schedule that enables to pair family vacation with event trip
- options/measures applied to the overall organisation of the event to be eligible and covered by the project's budget allocated to partners
- develop guidelines to welcome attendees such as children, partners, LGBTIQA+ families, pregnant people, relatives with disabilities, caregivers

> Resources/reference documents:

- [Supporting reconciliation of work, family and private life. Good practices](#) / European Institute for Gender Equality
- [Family-friendly workplaces. Overview of policies and initiatives in Europe](#) / European Commission

>> TRANS-lighthouses is committed to assessing the extent to which it can introduce specific measures to facilitate the reconciliation of professional activity and personal/family life, namely in the case of family-friendly events.

Accessible events

Created by Cristina Diaz from Nour Project

> Key aspects/features on accessibility:

- > It is important to think about accessibility for those who will present at the event and also for those who will attend
- > Ask openly before the event what is necessary to serve each participant
- > For a long event you need to think about accessible accommodation
- > Event presentations must be sent to the organiser. This practice makes it much easier for sign language translators
- > Activate captions on any video used in the presentation
- > Have sign language interpreters
- > Food: Clearly indicate allergens and gluten-free, vegan, vegetarian, or other options.
- > Consider those who may be in a wheelchair or have other mobility impairments
- > Consider access and space for service dogs
- > Encourage hourly breaks
- > Accessible parking
- > Is the event location close to public transport? Is the public transport that serves this route accessible?
- > Accessible bathrooms
- > Are the lights adjustable so you can control the brightness of the room? Good lighting helps people with hearing impairments read lips or communicate using sign language.

>> TRANS-lighthouses is committed to assessing the extent to which it can introduce specific measures to facilitate accessibility to events.

<p>Accessible website</p> <p><small>Created by Isabelle from Nour Project</small></p>	<p>> Key aspects/features on accessibility:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) colour and contrast between figures/text and background 2) have voice recognition 3) texts that can be recognized and read by text reader tools⁶ 4) have a clean and clear design, as simple as possible 5) have a space (or an email contact) for people with disabilities to report accessibility problems 6) the website must be tested by people with different types of disabilities 7) free tool for a type of virtual assistant that uses sign language on websites 8) have contrast options and letter changes 9) make navigation as simple as possible 10) fonts must be readable and accessible 11) being able to access with quality on your cell phone <p>> Web Content Accessibility Guidelines - https://www.w3.org/WAI/standards-guidelines/wcag/</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Following these guidelines will make content more accessible to a wider range of people with disabilities, including accommodations for blindness and low vision, deafness and hearing loss, limited movement, speech disabilities, photosensitivity, and combinations of these, and some accommodation for learning disabilities and cognitive limitations - But will not address every user's need for people with these disabilities. - These guidelines address accessibility of web content on desktops, laptops, tablets, and mobile devices. - Following these guidelines will also often make web content more usable to users in general. <p>>> TRANS-lighthouses is committed to assessing the extent to which it can introduce these guidelines into the specification definitions and development of its website.</p>
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Table 32: Accessible communication and interaction: practices and concerns

References for checking accessibility	
European Accessibility Act	https://www.inclusion-europe.eu/european-accessibility-act/
Accessibility in events	https://accessibleportugal.com/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/accessibilidade-eventos_web.pdf
Free accessibility website checker:	https://accessmonitor.accessibilidade.gov.pt/
A leading Portuguese accessibility website:	https://www.dges.gov.pt/pt

Table 33: References for checking accessibility

Accessible communication status report & evaluation:

The guidelines for accessible communication and interaction remain the same, providing a consistent framework for our efforts. We have made tangible progress in accommodating several key areas, demonstrating our commitment to fostering inclusive participation.

In the realm of digital interaction, the measures to address online video conferencing fatigue are now in place. Furthermore, the use of meeting signs to encourage active listening and fluid participation in assemblies has been successfully integrated into our standard meeting practice.

Beyond the meeting room, we have found ways to support work/family reconciliation. Specifically, we can now accommodate the needs of pregnant participants by offering a video option for those who cannot attend in-person meetings. Similarly, we have made arrangements to welcome participants with child care responsibilities, allowing them to bring family and children to events, thus removing a significant barrier to their full involvement. These steps reflect our ongoing effort to ensure that personal circumstances do not preclude professional engagement.

> Web Content Accessibility Guidelines

This evaluation assesses the TRANS-lighthouses website against the eleven key aspects of accessibility outlined in the project's internal guidelines, based on the Web Content Accessibility Guidelines from Web Accessibility Initiative (WAI). The assessment is based on a visual and technical review of the website.

⁶ In this matter of the text, it is necessary to be very careful because it is not only the format that may or may not be compatible with screen reader programs, the words may not be read correctly. Even though today there are software options that read, for example, "tod@s" "todxs", many people still use softwares that cannot read this type of supposedly accessible language.

Aspect	Status	Observation
<i>Colour and contrast</i>	Mostly met	The main body text color (<i>rgb: 68, 79, 76</i>) on a white background (<i>rgb: 255, 255, 255</i>) offers a contrast ratio of approximately 10.3:1 , which exceeds the WCAG AA standard of 4.5:1 . However, on the front page, the white text used over the background image, as well as the text in the orange footer section, may have insufficient contrast against the varying background colors.
<i>Voice recognition</i>	Not met	No interface feature for built-in voice recognition for navigation or input.
<i>Texts readable by text reader tools</i>	Met	The site is built using standard web technologies with clear HTML structure (headings, links, paragraphs), which generally ensures compatibility with screen reader tools.
<i>Clean and clear design</i>	Met	The design is clean, and uncluttered. The layout is simple, with a clear header, main content blocks, and a footer, which contributes to ease of use.
<i>Space to report accessibility problems</i>	Not met	No dedicated link or contact information explicitly for reporting accessibility issues was found. The footer includes a "Contact us" link, but it is not specifically designated for disability-related feedback.
<i>Tested by people with disabilities</i>	Not met	No testing of the website has been done so far by people with different types of disabilities.
<i>Sign language virtual assistant tool</i>	Not met	No sign language virtual assistant tool.
<i>Contrast options and letter changes</i>	Not met	No accessibility widget or control panel that allows users to adjust contrast, font size, or font type directly on the site.
<i>Simple navigation</i>	Met	The primary navigation is simple, clear, and consistently placed in the header, with a logical structure of dropdown menus for sub-sections.
<i>Readable and accessible fonts</i>	Met	The font used is a clean, sans-serif typeface that is highly readable at standard sizes, contributing positively to the overall accessibility.
<i>Access with quality on a cell phone</i>	Met	The site structure has a responsive design, which is the modern standard for ensuring quality access across different devices, including mobile phones.

The website has been developed with a focus on core accessibility principles, including a clean design, simple navigation, and readable fonts. Crucially, the site uses a clear HTML structure and readable font to ensure the content is readily accessible by text reader tools.

A pragmatic approach has been adopted for features not yet implemented, balancing resource allocation with user benefit. The decision to forego a dedicated sign language virtual assistant is based on the assessment that individuals who use sign language are typically proficient in reading standard text. The significant resources required for this specialized tool would not yield a proportionate increase in accessibility benefits beyond what the current text structure provides.

Furthermore, the process for reporting issues has been integrated into the existing ethical reporting framework. The "Ethics partners" page describes various channels for all types of ethical issues, and creating separate, dedicated spaces would unnecessarily complicate the site's structure and the reporting process.

However, the features concerning testing by people with different types of disabilities and providing user-controlled contrast options and letter changes are recognized as high-priority. These two aspects are considered essential next steps and are to be scheduled for future implementation.

Monitoring and evaluation

3. Monitoring and evaluation

In addition to defining indicators that allow us to evaluate the effectiveness of our communication, dissemination and exploration efforts, the project also incorporates a reflexive monitoring framework, as well as measurement and assessment frameworks and referenced guidelines for monitoring and evaluation.

3.1. Reflexive monitoring

Reflexive monitoring, as set out in the framework in task 6.1, applies across work packages, including communication, dissemination and exploitation of results, which are also transversally operationalised. It requires finding time for reflection in the framework of work packages' activities. Enabling a learning environment provides:

- insight into the progress of the project in real time;
- assessment of processes of learning-by-doing and doing-by-learning in terms of goals achievement;
- learning outcomes.

Figure 14: Reflexive monitoring: find time for reflection and enable a learning environment

Our reflexive monitoring process is designed to be an active learning mechanism, moving beyond descriptive accounts to extract critical insights and lessons learned from the project's implementation. This section summarizes the key results and strategic adjustments derived from our monitoring activities, emphasizing adaptive management and continuous improvement rather than merely detailing technical procedures.

Status report & evaluation of Reflexive monitoring:

Reflexive Monitoring (RM) has been integrated into the project's Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation activities plan as a mechanism to strengthen mutual learning, stakeholder engagement, and allowed the project to adapt and improve over time. A series of internal webinars introduced consortium members to the RM approach and encouraged them to reflect on progress, share lessons learned, and identify key changes and challenges. These sessions strengthened internal communication and informed the development of relevant and grounded dissemination materials

RM has shaped several key outputs, including *the preliminary guidelines for citizen science* (D6.7), *the living framework for social mobilization* (D6.1), and participatory tools such as the NBS Cards and the Board Game. These materials have been designed to reflect the needs and realities of local communities, young people, and policy stakeholders. By doing so, RM has contributed to more effective exploitation of project results, supporting their practical use and wider uptake potential.

Although maintaining momentum and coordinating data across work packages has presented challenges and required ongoing effort, RM continues to be a valuable tool for encouraging collaboration and co-creation.

3.2. Revision and updates

Since the initial communication, dissemination and exploitation plan (D1.1), learning outcomes emerging from reflexive monitoring are feeding into the communication, dissemination and exploitation plan, tools, materials and activities, making the most of internal communication expertise and resources to document the project implementation. Therefore, this second (*and later the third versions at month 40*) constitute updates and reports on the implementation of the plan that defines strategies, activities and expected results according to different target audiences, corresponding messages and tools. A key aspect of revisions made to the communication, dissemination and exploitation efforts is based on the first periodic review, which is outlined in the following sub-sections.

3.2.1 Implementation of evaluator comments from PR1

This section details the actions taken in response to the feedback and recommendations provided by evaluators during the first periodic report related to enhancing the communication, dissemination, and exploitation strategies. As a response, a dedicated workshop during the 7th consortium meeting and a number of meetings have been held with a communication expert and a communication officer from CES. The results were a number of measures to extend and fine-tune communication, dissemination and exploitation strategies. The three coming sections addressed specific comments from the reviewers regarding 1) communication, 2) dissemination, and 3) exploitation.

3.2.1.1. Communication

The evaluators noted a limited social media presence, questioning its effectiveness for attracting website visitors and achieving broader reach beyond local events. They recommended reconsidering regional and global approaches to audience engagement.

Status report of implementation of PR1 comments on communication:

The original Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan (outlined in Deliverable 1.1) briefly mentioned Social media as a component in the project's digital strategy but did not elaborate on a comprehensive strategy or its role in broader outreach.

In response to the evaluators' feedback, the D1.7 plan has been updated to:

Re-evaluate social media strategy

- Since PR1 the project has increased its focus on communication and has adopted a more active engagement. For example, by increasing its social media presence and doubling the aimed amount of posts.
- D1.7 now includes a more detailed approach to social media, confirming active platforms and reporting on key metrics (e.g., followers, engagement rate, reach, top-performing posts).

Website reach

- Since PR1, the project has regularly documented analytics of its digital media presence (For detailed information, see section 2.4.5). The project website has so far been the most successful channel, exceeding its annual target reach (as outlined in the Key Performance Indicators) by 450%. This directly responds to the concern about attracting visitors to the website.

3.2.1.2. Dissemination

Evaluators emphasized the need for a coherent strategy to attract website visitors, widen dissemination channels, and increase engagement with broader stakeholders at member state - and European levels. They specifically suggested greater use of social media and website improvements to highlight lessons and stories of activities.

Status report of implementation of PR1 comments on dissemination:

The original Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan provided a preliminary selection of events and publication channels as well as mentioned website development and social media. However the initial plan lacked a detailed strategy for wider impact.

To address the PR1 recommendations, the updated D1.7. plan now includes:

Coherent dissemination strategy:

- Since PR1, there has also been an increased focus on strategic dissemination. The Steering Committee has held a number of meetings specifically dedicated to the dissemination strategy and organised workshops with the whole consortium. As a result, the project has adopted a detailed publication strategy (see section 2.4.4.). Furthermore, the updated CDE plan now covers the implementation status and results of key activities, target audiences, channels, and tools (See section 2.3), showcasing a more structured approach to dissemination.

Expanded dissemination:

- D1.7 (See section 2.4.4) includes updated lists of events and publications, along with status reports and tracking sheets, demonstrating an expansion and more rigorous monitoring of dissemination efforts.
- The project has developed and is continuously evaluating and updating event & publication tracking sheets.

Increased stakeholder engagement:

- The D1.7 report, particularly in sections related to communication and interaction adapted to local contexts (Section 2.4.3), includes progress reports on activities undertaken, suggesting increased engagement with various stakeholders.

3.2.1.3. Exploitation

Evaluators noted the absence of a distinct exploitation plan and a lack of consideration for Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) in completed or planned deliverables.

Status report of implementation of PR1 comments on exploitation:

The initial plan identified Key Performance Indicators (KPI) and Key Exploitable Results (KER) but did not present a distinct, comprehensive exploitation plan or explicitly address IPR.

To address the PR1 feedback, the D1.7 plan has been updated to:

Development of the exploitation plan

- D1.7 (See section 3.3) now includes a new column in Table 31 for "status and progress reporting" for Key Performance Indicators (KPI) and Key Exploitable Results (KER), indicating a more mature approach to identifying and reporting on KPIs and KERs, which forms the basis of an exploitation plan. The overall structure of D1.7 also suggests a more comprehensive approach to exploitation.

Intellectual property rights:

- The suggestion from the reviewer to make research template agreements reusable by other projects. In response to the reviewers comment, an Authorship Policy has been developed and implemented within the project. Research outcomes and scientific publications are expected to reflect integrity and transparency, which are fundamental for advancing knowledge and maintaining trust within the research community. Proper attribution of authorship is an essential

part of these values, ensuring that all individuals who have significantly contributed to the project receive appropriate recognition.

- The Authorship Policy establishes clear guidelines for determining authorship in all outputs generated in the TRANS-lighthouses project and has been designed in line with recognised ethical standards and best practices. It ensures that credit is fairly assigned to those who contribute to the conception, execution and writing of research, while maintaining accountability for the integrity of the work. By adhering to this policy, the project aims to uphold transparency, prevent disputes, and ensure that research outputs meet the highest ethical standards. All contributors are expected to be familiar with and follow this policy in their research activities. The full policy is provided in Deliverable D7.2 - OEI - Requirement No. 2.

3.3. Key performance indicators and key exploitable results

Project's key results	Activities	Indicators / KPI	2023	2024	2025	2026	Key exploitable results / KER (preliminary identification)	Status and progress report
			X					
1. The project's successful implementation → Awareness about activities and results	Definition of communication policy, procedures and objectives by the steering committee	- 1 communication, dissemination and exploitation plan	X					Completed & implemented
		- 2 updated versions of the plan, including reporting on implementation			X	X		Version 2 completed, version 3 Month 39 of the project.
		- 1 kick-off event	X				> June 2023, Azores	Completed (Azores 2023)
		- 1 international conference/summer school				X	>Academic and practitioner utilisation (via publications) in further research & innovation actions. >Training materials can be used by partners & stakeholders to organise the same or similar programmes.	Planned for month M40.
		- 1 closing event				X		Planned: Brussels M42 2026
		- 3 public communications/ exhibitions/workshops in EC events		X	X	X		Goal reached: 3 events completed, one more planned.
		- 3 public communications/ sessions/workshops in networking events		X	X	X		Goal reached and exceeded: 9 events,
		- 6 participations of partners in national, regional and international events		X	X	X		Goal reached and exceeded: 12 events
	Design of communication tools to support the development of communication materials	- 1 project brand and application guidelines	X					Completed & implemented (D1.1)
		- 1 dissemination package with communication templates and materials	X	X	X	X		Completed & implemented (D1.3)
		- 1 project website / 4-stage development	X	X	X	X		Stage 1,2,3 completed & implemented. Stage 4 initiated.
		- 1 digital template of newsletter	X	X				Completed & implemented
		- 2 social media accounts created	X	X				Completed (<i>LinkedIn, Youtube, Padlet</i>)
	Development of communication materials	- 1 database with images, news and communication and dissemination inputs and metrics	X	X	X	X		Implemented (<i>see section on Monitoring tools</i>)
		- 1 fact sheet/project overview, updated at least once, translated in local languages	X	X	X	X		Update and translation along project
		- 1 leaflet/flyer/brochure, updated at least once, translated in local languages		X	X	X		Material developed, update and translation along project
		- 1 poster about the project, updated at least once, translated in local language	X	X	X	X		Update and translation along project.

	- 8 posters of pilot cases, 10 posters of assessment cases, updated at least once, translated in local languages	X	X	X	X	> Update and translation along project >Development into implementation stories > Potential for future projects and/or organisations to write up their experiences using this template >Reference materials for training purposes	Initial posters completed Mid-project posters in progress, not yet translated.
	- 2 blog posts in the project website per partner during the lifetime of the project		X	X	X		In progress: 6 out of 16 blog posts published.
	- 200 unique visitors to the website per year		X	X	X		Reached and surpassed by 450%.
	- 100 downloads for public deliverables during the lifetime of the project		X	X	X		In progress, public deliverables were published to the website after PR1 was concluded.
	- 2 newsletters per year		X	X	X		Implemented, 2 out of 5 newsletter published. Remaining planned for M32, M38, and M42. Published newsletters can be found in the resource section of the project's website.
	- 500 mailing list subscribers		X	X	X		Evolving reach, current: 76 subscribers.
	- 5 press releases in English	X	X	X	X		Implemented and surpassed.
	- at least 1 post in social media account per month		X	X	X		Implemented and ongoing.
	- 300 followers in social media account		X	X	X		Evolving reach, current 245 followers.
	- 1 institutional video, translated in local languages			X	X	Reference material for training purposes	Completed: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Tmizd3WVqp8&t=989s
Divulgence of the project in the websites and newsletters of international networks and stakeholders, traditional media	- 4 media appearances (i.e. TV, radio)		X	X	X		Reached and exceeded: <i>Total number of times the project is mentioned in media outlets: 6.</i>
	- 3 publications in specialised magazines/journals		X	X	X		Ongoing: 2/ 3 publications completed.
	- 5 featured project presentations in specialised blogs and forums		X	X	X		Ongoing, 2/5 Submitted and accepted to the NetworkNature blog..
Development of interactions among consortium members, as well as tools and platforms for project management and team communication	- monthly online meetings of the steering committee	X	X	X	X		Implemented: ongoing.
	- 10 consortium meetings (in-person/online) and general assemblies	X	X	X	X		Implemented: 7/10 meetings at this stage of the project.
	- 3 technical visits to pilot/assessment cases		X	X	X		Exceeded: Completed: X (Azores, Rome, Brussels, Buenos Aires., Cáceres, Madrid) planned: 2 (Upper Allgau, Cyprus, Roskilde)
	- 2 monitoring reports per year by work package leaders	X	X	X	X		Ongoing, completed after each Consortium meeting.
	- 1 set of guidelines on project's workflow and standard quality procedures		X	X	X	Methodological resources that can support awareness raising and development of guidelines of partners, stakeholders and other research and innovation actions, appropriate action and the realisation of good practices	Implemented: External ethics advisory board, ethical guidelines , gender checklist for events, sustainability guidelines, accessibility guidelines (see sections 3.5: Assessment frameworks for detailed information).

						(e.g. ethics, gender, sustainability, accessibility)			
		- 1 Gender Equality and Diversity (GED) focal point appointed, working with the steering committee		X	X	X	Appointed.		
		- 1 internal communication platform	X	X	X	X	Implemented (<i>Basecamp</i>).		
		- 1 cloud storage space		X	X	X	Implemented (<i>Google Drive</i>).		
2. Community of practice → Plurality of models, strategies and findings showcased from a diversity of contexts	Knowledge sharing and synergies building among partners, and in the framework of clustering activities with other projects	- 2 internal and/or open webinars per year, with presentations of horizontal partners and discussions with the members of the consortium, associated partners and invited participants		X	X	X	Exceeded: Internal webinars: 21 Open webinars: Completed: 6, planned: 3		
		- 1 clustering with projects/liaison with networks (starting from EU funded projects)		X	X	X	NBS Task forces collaboration in the form of joint messaging, events and communications campaigns to ensure visibility	Implemented (Network Nature, participation in Task Forces 1,2,3,4, & 6)	
		- 2 collaborations with sibling projects		X	X	X	Joint communication and dissemination activities, scientific exchange	Implemented (COEVOLVERS & NATURESCAPES).	
	Involving associated partners in a community of practice	- 2 webinars per year	X	X	X	X		Ongoing (2023: 2 webinars, 2024: 2 webinars, 2025: 1 webinar held in Spring, 1 planned in Fall). Additionally, there are plans for a thematic webinar on gender and nature-based solutions.	
		- 1 consortium event and/or technical visit			X	X	X	Completed. 2 workshops on ecofeminist perspectives on nature-based solutions were held in Buenos Aires (Argentina) and Coimbra (Portugal), in April and June 2025, respectively. These involved technical visits as well, by the CES task leader to Buenos Aires and by the representative of the associated partner University of Buenos Aires to CES. Associated partner Municipality of Sao Paulo also held a technical visit to Coimbra in October 2024.	
		- 2 reports based on the compilation and analysis on knowledge sharing and synergies building		X		X		2 reports completed: one by CES (on the overall work of the international associated partners network, and one by the associated partner Rede RIU on their project analysing potentials and challenges of integration of nature-based solutions in social solidarity economy initiatives in Parana (Brazil). Additional reports (one by each associated partner) are under preparation.	
		- 1 publication with non-European countries, based on North-South cross comparison				X		Academic and practitioner utilisation in research and innovation actions	In progress. Discussions are underway with the representative of associated partner University of Buenos Aires to write a paper based on the two workshops (held in Buenos Aires and Coimbra) on ecofeminist perspectives on nature-based solutions
	13. Expanded conceptual framework and assessment for NBS	Scientific dissemination of expanded conceptual framework and	- 4 papers in international referenced publications		X	X		Academic and practitioner utilisation in research and innovation actions	In progress: 2/4 completed.

→ Living knowledge to be co-disseminated	assessment for NBS in publications & conferences	- 6 presentations and publications with international and referenced conferences		X	X	X	Academic and practitioner utilisation in research and innovation actions	Goal exceeded: 17 presentations in total, 3 of which have conference proceeding publications and one more forthcoming (Nov 2025).
	Inclusive knowledge and practice dissemination, by means of unconventional initiatives of knowledge sharing, such as local community events, local media, and networks	- 8 local community events of scientific knowledge dissemination in Living Knowledge Labs			X	X		Completed and surpassed: A total of 49 local community events of scientific knowledge dissemination have been held in the Living Knowledge Labs
		- 6 featured project presentations in local media	X	X	X	X		Ongoing: 5/6 presentations completed.
		- 3 clustering and liaison with networks		X	X	X	Joint messaging, events and communications campaigns to ensure visibility.	Implemented: Ongoing
4. Science for citizens and policy makers → Leaving no one behind in research and long-term relationships	Results are shared and made accessible throughout the research process by means of internal living documents	- 2 internal living documents to inform the project ongoing activities and disseminate internally among partners and local stakeholders intermediates results		X	X		Joint messaging, events and communications campaigns to ensure visibility.	Implemented. Dissemination & Communication tracing Google sheet. Basecamp Head Quarters message board.
		- translation of the primary English version into local languages by the respective consortium partners			X	X	Joint messaging, events and communications campaigns to ensure visibility.	Implemented within Task 6.4 (<i>Community website: https://translighthousescommunity.eu/</i>)
	Democracy labs	- 3 democracy labs		X	X	X	>Actionable knowledge for informed decision-making and tailored policies >Insights for workshops, policy briefs and learning cases	Exceeded: 5 Democracy labs held.
		- 3 policy briefs, infographics, videos and serious gaming produced to provide guidance for co-governance		X	X	X	>Actionable knowledge for informed decision-making and tailored policies >Training materials can be used by partners and stakeholders to support appropriate action and the realisation of good practices	4 Policy briefs completed 4 Learning cases completed Infographics: template completed, infographics for public Deliverables from PR1 completed. Videos: 1 completed, 1 in development. Serious gaming: 1 Board game with 4 versions (English, Portuguese, French, German) 1 set of interactive NBS cards with 2 versions (English, Portuguese) 1 geo-game completed
		- 5 learning cases/dilemmas to be created with local governments and civil society organisations		X	X	X	>Actionable knowledge for informed decision-making and tailored policies >Training materials can be used by partners and stakeholders to support appropriate action and the realisation of good practices	In development: Template completed, first learning case in development.
		- 2 animated videos on Lab Democracy for NBS		X	X	X	>Actionable knowledge for informed decision-making and tailored policies >Training materials can be used by partners and stakeholders to support appropriate action and the realisation of good practices	1 video completed in month 27, 1 video currently in development by ICLD.

5. Co-governance innovations towards co-creation of NBS → Replication and amplification	Production of transition roadmaps	- 3 roadmaps disseminated through workshops for co-governance, policy briefs, videos and serious gaming			X	X	>Actionable knowledge for informed decision-making and tailored policies >Training materials can be used by partners and stakeholders to support appropriate action and the realisation of good practices	Roadmaps will be produced in T4.4 during PR3 based on the analysis of the results from the assessment activities.	
	Development of research and guidelines to amplify the involvement of youth and older adults in the co-creation of NBS	- 8 dissemination and training workshops, one per pilot		X	X			Completed: 7 online workshops and one 3-day in person training in Trento. M(13-15) by Jangada	
		- 8 videos, one per pilot, produced by youth				X	X	>Joint messaging, events and communications campaigns to ensure visibility. >Development into implementation stories >Reference material for training purposes	In progress: 2/8 videos produced.
		- 1 pilot introduction of NBS co-creation and co-governance content in college disciplines					X	>Training materials can be used by partners and stakeholders to support appropriate action and the realisation of good practices	Exceeded: 6 introductions of NBS co-creation and co-governance content in college disciplines.
6. Living Knowledge(s) Labs → Visibility and documentation	The communication strategies for social mobilisation and citizen engagement are devised with the communities and participants, supported by frameworks, guidelines and tools developed in WP6	- 8 Living Knowledge Labs established and documented		X	X	X		Established and documented (WP5)	
		- 4 NBS participatory budgeting processes organised to select locally the NBS				X	X	In progress, supported by workshop and bilateral meetings.	
	- 8 sets of graphic and text material (one per pilot) for a diffused awareness about the aims of the specific pilot		X	X	X		Finished: Created based on bilateral meetings held during month 25.		
	- 8 adaptations of the project's communication materials by teams for local use and dissemination		X	X	X		Texts have not yet been translated by teams for local use and dissemination.		
	The documentation of the overall design and implementation process of the pilot cases applies a cross-medial approach	- 1 playbook co-produced with the participants of the 8 pilot cases				X	X	>Joint messaging, events and communications campaigns to ensure visibility. >Development into implementation stories >Reference material for training purposes	In progress
		- 1 database with labs' images, news and other relevant communication and dissemination inputs and metrics		X	X	X		Established and ongoing	
7. Citizen science global framework for NBS → Community-based communication and assessment	Mobilisation of citizens' local knowledges and development of trust	- 1 living global framework of citizen science for NBS				X	X	Based on citizen science results and resources coming from different work packages, illustrates examples covering relevant practice areas, and motivates the adoption of reflexive monitoring to advance the NBS science and practice	In progress: Completion by M38.
		- 1 portfolio of participatory methods				X	X	>Actionable knowledge based on methodology and tools >Development into implementation stories >Reference material for training purposes	In progress: Completion by M36

		- 1 digital platform co-created with youth inhabitants of the pilot cases, including 8 subsites			X	X	>Educommunication >Development into implementation stories >Reference material for training purposes	Completed M15 by Jangada
		- 1 social media account followed by a diversity of local stakeholders and citizens in each lab			X	X		Completed M15 by Jangada
		- 1 media campaign developed with youth in each lab			X	X	>> Joint messaging, events and communications campaigns to ensure visibility.	In progress until the end of the project
	Exploration of data usability and tools (contexts and profiles):	- 1 data usability demonstrator			X		>> Actionable knowledge based on methodology and tools >> Development into implementation stories >> Reference material for training purposes	In progress, but delayed due to the pilot Implementation which have generated delays in the data collection and consequently the data usability demonstrator has been postponed for PR3.
		- 1 report on digital and low-tech tools building on how these tools have been explored in the pilot cases to support participatory assessment and embedded in the implementation of NBS				X		In progress, submission M39.
8. Research data and knowledge → Accessibility, preservation and ethics compliance	Compliance with open access principles	- 1 data management plan and 1 communication, dissemination and exploitation plan integrating principles	X		X	X		Completed M5.
		- 20 resources available on the project's website to be downloaded with no restrictions		X	X	X	Academic and practitioner utilisation in further research and innovation actions	In progress: 16/20 available.
		- 1 Zenodo TRANS-lighthouses community	X	X	X	X	Academic and practitioner utilisation in further research and innovation actions	Implemented.
		- 3 publications on open research platforms, including the Horizon Results Platform		X	X	X	Academic and practitioner utilisation in further research and innovation actions	Exceeded: 7 open access publications (1 book, 3 conference proceedings + one forthcoming, one forthcoming scientific journal article, 1 other publication.)
		- 1 publication with processing charge/fee afforded by the project to grant free access to readers			X	X	Academic and practitioner utilisation in further research and innovation actions	Reached: 1 article in scientific journal.
	Management and protection:	- 1 consortium agreement with detailed regulations regarding the protection and exploitation of project results		X				Completed and implemented.
		- 1 data management plan, updating and reporting on its implementation twice until the end of the project	X		X	X		Data management plan version 1 completed and implemented. Version 2: M30, version 3: M42.
	Elaboration and application of ethics requirements	- 4 ethics deliverables under work package 7	X	X	X	X		In progress: Number 1 and 2 submitted. Planned: No. 3: M36. No. 4 M48.
		- 1 external independent ethics advisor/board	X	X	X	X		Implemented M5 (see D7.1)
		- 1 guide on research ethics and inclusive participation for NBS		X			Research methodology/methods that can be exploited in various research and innovation actions	Completed in M20 (D.2.1)
	- activation of 8 focal points and local ethics channels, including modalities for reporting		X	X	X		Established in all 8 pilot cases (see D.7.3, M30).	

	- 2 meetings of the consortium with the external independent ethics advisor/board		X	X	X		- 1 meeting completed during Consortium Meeting #6 (M21). - 1 meeting planned for the Final conference of the project (M41).
	- 2 webinars for the dissemination and appropriation of ethics principles, guidelines, procedures, requirements		X	X			- 1 internal webinar: <i>Ethical Lighthouses: Guiding the path from theory to practices</i> (M21). - 2 public webinars: <i>Ecofeminism & NBS</i> (M30) <i>Social Solidarity economy</i> (M30)
	- translation of the primary English version of ethics documents into local languages by respective consortium partners		X	X	X	Research methodology/methods that can be exploited in various research and innovation actions, but tailored to needs and target groups	In progress.

Table 34: Indicators for monitoring and evaluation (KPI) and identification of exploitable results (KER), updated version.

3.4. Monitoring tools

TRANS-lighthouses project has developed tracking tools to support the collection of data about dissemination and communication activities for reporting purposes. These are collaborative tools which enables all partners to:

- be aware of their obligations in relation to communication and dissemination;
- inform and keep track of communication and dissemination activities and outcomes;
- support the consortium internal reporting, as well as to report to the funding authority.

As detailed in the table below, these tools cover: *consortium channels*; *dissemination reporting*; *communication reporting*; *press and media*.

MONITORING TOOLS									
Consortium channels									
2	PARTNER	WEBSITE	Website Reach	LINKEDIN	LinkedIn Reach				
3	PARTNERS								
4									
5									
6									
7									
8									
+ Consortium Channels Dissemination Reporting Communication Reporting Press and Media									
Dissemination reporting									
2	Instructions for filling in this sheet: Please mark here events where you speak about TRANS-lighthouses. These do not necessarily need to be your own events. It can be online sessions, and events organized by other partners where you are a speaker. It's MANDATORY to fill in all this information.								
3	Dissemination activity name	Date of dissemination	Partner Responsible/ Participating	Organizer Name	What? Type of Dissemination	Who? Target Audience	Description of the objective/s specific project output (m	Why?	
20									
21									
22									
23									
24									
25									
26									
27									
+ Consortium Channels Dissemination Reporting Communication Reporting Press and Media									
Communication reporting									
2	Communication Activity Details								
3	Instructions for filling in this sheet: Count each post/newsletter mention/website update etc. as a separate entry/line, even if it communicated the same content. Fill in the available data on impressions and eng. It's MANDATORY to fill in all the information.								
4	Communication Activity Name (short label as described in the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan)	Partner Responsible	Date of Communication	Description	Who? Target audience	How? Communication channel	OUTCOME	Page # (websites, blogs, news)	
5									
6									
7									
8									
9									
10									
11									
12									
13									
+ Consortium Channels Dissemination Reporting Communication Reporting Press and Media									
Press and media									
2	Name of media outlet	Journalist/contact person	Country	Contact Owner	Topic of proposed publication	Contacted by	Link to published material (if applicable)	Date of publication	Comment
3	1) When you send out press information, please mark in columns E-F that you've done it, and add a link to the ready material in columns G-H if it gets published. As probably some partners in the consortium have contacts with the same media outlets, please check in the table if someone else has already reached out to the same media/journalist before you with the same topic. In order to avoid duplications.								
4	2) If you send more than one press info to the same media/journalist add a new row below their name, and fill in again columns E-I with info about the specific publication.								
5									
6									
7									
8									
9									
+ Consortium Channels Dissemination Reporting Communication Reporting Press and Media									

Table 35: Monitoring tools

Status report & evaluation of monitoring tools:

The implementation and integration of these monitoring tools across the project has proven very effective. All partners are using the tools, and the process has become embedded in the project's routine operations. The tools have improved the efficiency and accuracy of activity tracking, particularly during periodic reporting cycles.

Partners have reported that the tools are intuitive and easy to use, reducing administrative burden and ensuring consistent data entry. Moreover, the centralized format has allowed comparative analysis, which has allowed the coordination and communication team to assess impact, identify potential areas needing attention, and strategically adjust outreach plans as needed.

Overall, the monitoring tools have been instrumental in supporting the project's communication and dissemination objectives, promoting accountability, and ensuring alignment with Horizon Europe requirements.

Risk assessment, ethics compliance, and data privacy

4. Risk assessment, ethics compliance, and data privacy

4.1. Risk assessment

4.1.1. General risks in international and interdisciplinary projects

When coordinating a European project with partners from various countries and diverse backgrounds, such as academia, NGOs, municipalities, etc., one of the significant risks is the potential lack of coherence in terminology and transversal communication of key messages. In addition to conceptual differences among project partners, this risk might arise also due to differences in language, disciplinary perspectives, and cultural nuances.

Within Task 2.1 of the project, the project has developed a conceptual framework which can support in mitigating this risk. This framework provides a cohesive understanding of key concepts and can serve as a guide for aligning communication efforts within the project consortium and throughout the project lifecycle. It serves as a reference point for all project deliverables and ensures consistency in messaging across all project partners, both nationally and internationally.

Furthermore, the conceptual framework is actively utilised to guide discussions within the TRANS-lighthouses consortium. This collaborative approach ensures that all partners are on the same page regarding terminology and the project's key messages.

In summary, the conceptual framework plays a crucial role in mitigating the risk of coherence in terminology and communication/key messages within international and interdisciplinary projects like TRANS-Lighthouses. By providing a structured approach to conceptualising and communicating key project concepts, it fosters alignment, clarity, and consistency across all project activities and stakeholders.

4.1.2. Communications critical risks as screened for grant preparation

Communications critical risks as screened for grant preparation			
Risk #	Description / Proposed mitigation measures	WP	Outcome/Mitigation measures (Month 30)
2	Internal communication problems (low) Review communication plan; improve the channels and focal points for communication.	WP1	<p>Preliminary communication channels from D1.1 have been implemented and are successfully in use. The Basecamp for centralized communication and task management is very effective. Moreover, Google Workspace streamlined document storage and collaboration through a shared Drive. Moreover, frequent meetings have been effective in keeping a strong communication among partners.</p> <p>In addition to the conceptual framework, 4 other frameworks have been of significant importance (WP2: Reference Framework Towards Reciprocal Human-Nature Relationships, Reference Framework for learning to unlearn; WP4: Governance Archetypes Framework for NBS; WP6: Living Framework on social mobilisation and Citizen Engagement, Reflexive monitoring, Citizen Science Framework). These frameworks have created a coherent alignment between the different concepts, approaches, tasks and work packages that compose the project.</p>

8	Continuous impacts of COVID-19, restrictions for in-person meetings (medium -high) Use of digital tools, formats and meetings, work in small groups, host meetings in open-air settings in nature where safety and physical distance can be achieved easily, 1:1 formats etc.	WP3	There have been successful use of digital tools (online meetings) and in-person meetings have been feasible without restrictions impacting meeting outcomes in any significant ways.
9	Engagement of stakeholders and citizens not so familiar with digital tools (low) Toolbox with approaches to address and target these groups, work package 6 dedicated to this topic.	WP3	Work package 6 dedicated to this topic, with a toolbox with approaches to address and target these groups. This did occur partially in some of the Pilots. However, Task 5.5 and Task 6.5 are implementing analogue-to-digital integration to overcome this challenge.
18	Stakeholders expectation mismatch for the project outputs (medium) Transparent and clear communication on the scientific outputs that are prioritised and expected in the research (i.e. why, how, what).	WP6	A workshop dedicated to the scientific outputs of each Work Package was held during the #7 Consortium meeting. Furthermore, significant efforts have been dedicated to aligning the above mentioned frameworks to achieve cross-framework coherence and continuity. This alignment and clear conceptualization has contributed to transparent communication of scientific outputs. The lighthouses typologies set the scene for researching different contexts of pilot and assessment cases, regarding their characteristics and needs in co-creating NBS. The typology was useful in organizing discussions and critical reflections to understand participatory culture, governance dynamics and societal and environmental issues concerning each pilot case.
19	Digital and low tech issues: Tools appropriation, delivery delay, technical limitations Propose many options to resolve problems.	WP6	Task 6.5 is dedicated to addressing this issue. As an additional measure, the project also invests in analogue-to-digital integration to overcome potential barriers related to limited digital literacy and infrastructure.

Table 36: Communications critical risks as screened for grant preparation. Updated version with Outcomes/Mitigation measures (M30).

4.1.3. SWOT analysis - Dissemination capacity of partners (Sep. 2023)

At the beginning of the project, Task 1.5 and Work Package 6 joined efforts to launch a communications survey to know the communication capabilities and tools/channels of each partner. The survey was followed by a workshop with key communication persons that were identified through the survey.

This communications survey was organised to assess objectives, environment and communicative capacity of partners, as shown in the table below (*further detailed in Annex 1 of Deliverable 1.1.*)

Overview of communications survey 1 (Sep. 2023) ⁷	
1. Contribution, doubt, or disagreement on communication goals <ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Communication goals (task 1.5) > Objectives of work package 6 > Another relevant communication objective to consider 	4. KPIs for measuring and evaluate strategic performance of actions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Use of indicators: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - visibility - engagement - conversion - sentiment - other relevant KPIs
2. Partners' communication environment <ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Limitations to the use of mass media or traditional channels > Media coverage area > Style and scope of the usual communication > Involvement culture of the private sector and civil society > Political dynamics > Cultural characteristics and diversity > Role and capacity of civil society > Existing related development efforts and communication campaigns 	5. Communication contacts and channels <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Communicational interface with the WP6 and Task 1.5 - Communication channels of the partners' organisation/entity
3. Communicative capacity of the partners' organisation/entity <ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Capacity for dissemination dissemination > Communication officer > Channels used to communicate, inform, disseminate, calls > Networks for dissemination 	

Table 37: Overview of communications survey 1 (Sep. 2023)

The results of the survey were compiled and analyzed in preparation of the assessment/review workshop conducted with the key communication persons.

⁷ For the full survey; See Deliverable 1.1, Annex 1. Communications survey; assessment of objectives, environment and communicative capacity of partners (Sep. 2023).

SWOT analysis - Capacity for dissemination of partners, based on communications survey 1 (Sep. 2023)

STRENGTHS

- > AI use on Community communication and citizen science in some team
- > Many communication vectors and materials: Email, Web, Newsletter, Social networks (Instagram, Twitter, Facebook, Tik Tok, Youtube...), Street action
- > All scales in terms of population and entities
- > All teams agree with WP6 objectives
- > Objectives address EU recommendations
- > Objectives in line with project's transversal dimension
- > Objectives promote a holistic and effective approach to community-centred communication and engagement.
- > Objectives involve the distinct dimensions of NBS communication
- > Digital devices or app
- > Gender equality sensibility
- > Different civil society organisations acting in the territories
- > All the teams have dissemination's capacity for the project results
- > The majority of the teams have someone responsible for communication
- > Ability for each team to call for participation when advertising an event or a call to action
- > Same monitoring indicators are needed for communication strategy assessment

WEAKNESSES

- > Youth and women are not clearly identified as target populations
- > Terminologies to precise or include: - dissemination - exploitation - "unlearning" - equitable participation - bidirectional - community empowerment and decentralisation
- > Include communication coming from the "outside" with project
- > Concrete tangible dimension of communication is missing
- > Some societies are not really "all inclusive" in terms of population origin
- > Two teams don't have someone dedicated/responsible for the communication management
- > No systematic/ professionalised dissemination of work to broader audience and civil society and lack of (human) resources to be very active "on the ground" and beyond projects (both are not rewarded by academic system)
- > Only a few numbers of teams make impact assessment after a communication campaign
- > In some teams:
 - Some communication departments are often overwhelmed.
 - Lack of internal communication department; lack of human resources with training in communication area
 - Lot to transfer to the local governments, with risk of overwhelming them with too much information and possible action items
 - Bureaucracy
 - Very small team
 - Lack of financial resources.
 - The academic calendar and the overload professors/researchers and students
 - The Location (kind of far from the City centre) reduce the possibilities of having own resources to reach the community, but will keep on working the synergies with other NGOs and entities)
 - Political adversary
 - HR need to particular project, fragmentation of network and administration
 - Impact of social communication
 - Big machine (institutional communication service)
 - Little organisation for communications support
 - Lack of training of the communications office team in specific area of project

OPPORTUNITIES

- > Continued commitment of the EU in NBS
- > Possibility to create a space for the customization of a 'NBS communication'
- > Media Ownership and pluralism (Belgium)
- > Different communication styles to prepare (formal and informal)
- > Diversity of public
- > Very active organisations (NGOs) in the territory that are carrying out communication actions
- > Diversity of languages: English, French, Portuguese, Spanish, Swahili, German
- > In some teams:
 - Publishing research results, interesting work and results to offer, knowledge also on interpretation, education (forest pedagogics!) and target groups for communication
 - Existing communication department
 - Team commitment to the proper development of the project; partner media with local newspaper (biweekly page); website to be able to function as a local link of the TRANS-lighthouses project
 - Close connections to municipalities in the Global South.
 - Researcher network specialised in various aspects of local democracy
 - Organisation are already well-known and prestigious
 - Pre-existing network with communication experience, well-structured news websites, broad reach, diversity focus, experience in environmental topics
 - Already active social networks / students can participate in the processes / other project where partners are involved and the direct participation of some of the members of the team in other Horizon projects
 - Large network, communication team and political visibility
 - Expertise in communicating science; good overall perspective of the target groups.
- > Scale of students, professors, employees.
- > Communication service already established for the top institutional level. Project teams already familiar with some communication tools like blogs or CMS administration.
- > Close collaboration with case and expertise in partitives methods
- > Existence of a communications office

NEEDS

THREATS

- > Flexibility/openness to adapt if new needs are identified or expressed
- > Adaptability
- > Conduct communication in the traditional or mainstream way; lack of innovation
- > Use the right material at the right level across institutions
- > Verified information
- > Coherence of communication strategy
- > Many political constraints:
 - Direct link or ongoing collaboration with political entities
 - Be careful about expressing opinions that are politically sensitive
 - Language requirements
 - Media regulation authorities
- > Tradition and religion forces
- > Be GDPR compliant
- > Various literacy rate
- > Citizens themselves are hard to involve
- > Some entities have their own communication strategies
- > "Bureaucratic" language (project presentation on [CORDIS website](#))
- > Conventional administrative regard, some established centralised culture can be an opponent
- > Male-centred communities
- > Strong presence of industry in some territories and communities

- For an academic institution, more and more professionalised outreach and dissemination to broader audiences - professional social media activities, better transfer of knowledge and bringing things "to the ground"
- Difficult to realise: time and in-person exchanges with actors "on the ground", supporting them in their efforts to get solutions implemented
- A vision on community-based communication in the context of a communication department in a big university
- Training, partnership in the diversification of channels and media
- Clearly defined angles of how the results are useful for communities in the Global South, and easily adaptable formats
- Researchers' time and efforts to participate in conference or learning opportunities with other local democracy researchers
- Facilitate team building and time management
- Larger funding to expand the team
- To involve more people (administrative / colleagues/ students) in the project communication needs
- Management of different actors, knowledge of hierarchical structure and political position of hierarchy, trust from associations and citizens
- External communication services, capacitation
- Integration between mailing lists and social networks
- Need support to identify which information is relevant or not for which media
- Support decided and available in the consortia is welcomed
- Involvement and training of the communications office team

Table 38: SWOT analysis - Capacity for dissemination of partners, based on the results of communications survey 1 (Sep. 2023).

Status report & evaluation of SWOT analysis:

The communications survey and the subsequent SWOT analysis (*Table 39*) have served as a foundational step for organizing and structuring the project's communication efforts.

This initial survey and analysis have yielded two significant organizational outcomes essential for the project's communication efforts:

- A comprehensive overview of partner capacity and available resources has been compiled using the SWOT analysis as a foundational reference. This information is detailed in Chapter 5 under the section "Responsible partners and resources," which outlines the current capabilities and assets dedicated to dissemination across the consortium.
- A dedicated group of "communications contact persons" was formally established at the beginning of the project as a communication interface with task 1.5 and WP6 who support:
 - the assessment of communication objectives, as well as the environment and communicative capacity of partners;
 - the refinement of key performance indicators (KPI) and key exploitable results (KER).

This group is composed of one designated person from each partner organization, who is responsible for submitting communication requests. The group maintains a regular meeting schedule, convening approximately every four months. This structured approach has been essential for organizing the communication efforts and ensuring coherence across the project.

Next steps and future analysis

To maintain momentum and ensure the communication strategy remains responsive to the project's evolving needs, a more in-depth analysis of the current situation of the identified strengths, weaknesses, risks, opportunities, and needs is required by the communication group. This comprehensive review is planned for early 2026. This forward-looking analysis will be critical for refining the dissemination strategy and maximizing the project's outreach and impact for the final year of the project.

4.2. Ethics compliance

In addition to the aforementioned ethical guidelines regarding images and messages ([Dóchas Guide to Ethical Communications 2023](#)), the TRANS-lighthouses project has its ethical compliance set out in:

- *Task 2.5:*
 - establishment of the principles and procedures to resolution and mediation of any conflicts and ethics issues;
 - establishment of local mechanism/focal point to respond to the ethics, human rights and gender issues in each local context;
 - continuous monitoring of the adequacy of procedures, methods and principles application;
 - development of guidelines (deliverable D2.1) co-constructed according to the conceptual framework of work package 2, including specificities, e.g. childhood, gender, functional diversity, older adults, race and ethnicity, citizenship status (migrant/refugee/asylum seeker condition), religious diversity, and priority groups of the project;
 - provision of ethics, gender and human rights indicators to be monitored and for the assessment of the project compliance with "Do No Significant Harm" principle (article 17 EU regulation 2020/852);
 - formulation of a code of ethics and conduct, inspired by human-nature and co-production principles.

- *Work package 7:*
 - consisting of 4 deliverables that sets out the 'ethics requirements' the project must comply with for any activity raising ethical issues;
 - appointment of 1 external independent ethics commission (deliverable D7.1);
 - provision of templates necessary for compliance with ethical procedures, including informed consent, information sheet, withdrawal declaration, among others.

In the framework of the OEI - Requirement No. 1 (deliverable D7.1), an External Ethical Advisory Board (EEAB) has been established, which was activated during the first year of the project. The EEAB will ensure adherence to the ethical guidelines that is defined in task 2.5 (deliverable D2.1 - Guide on research ethics and inclusive participation for NBS) and according to the highest ethical standards, namely [GDPR](#), [European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity](#), [Horizon Europe Guide on Ethics and Data Protection](#) (2021), [Horizon Europe Guide on Ethics in Social Sciences and Humanities](#) (2021). The documents produced and decisions taken by the EEAB will be carried out in line with these ethical standards. The international and national laws on ethical principles in each country are also involved, and the EEAB guides its action and promotes the commitment to respect EU-based values, such as respect for human dignity, freedom, democracy, equality, the rule of law and human rights, including the rights of minorities.

Accordingly, the project activities that include data collection are designed to respect and maintain privacy regulations, as mandated by GDPR. All participants of such activities are explicitly informed through written documents about the way their data will be handled, the purpose of their usage, who will have access to them, as well as their own rights in their data. Participants are also requested to declare their agreement to these approaches through a consent form. No personal data is collected unless absolutely necessary. In such cases, personal data is stored in secure servers with access to them granted only to specific persons of the consortium.

Moreover, in relation to activities of communication, dissemination and exploitation of results, specific attention is paid to informed consent, as well as to disclosing information about assessment and pilot cases through the external communication channels.

4.3. Data privacy

The TRANS-lighthouses' data management plan (v1, deliverable D1.2) outlines the specifics of the data that will be collected and/or generated through the entire span of the project, i.e. all data deriving from every activity that will be performed in the context of the project.

As regard to data privacy, as established in the data management plan:

- All project data are stored to Google Drive cloud servers using a commercial, non-public licence of Google Workspace that meets privacy and security requirements to comply with GDPR.
- The administrator of the Google Drive/Workspace account ensures that access to the data is only possible to project team members according to a data classification policy, which organises them into user groups determined by the steering committee.
- The identification of the team members are ensured by using authentication processes.
- In compliance with [GDPR](#), a data region policy has been set to ensure that data is stored exclusively to servers geographically located in Europe.
- The project TRANS-lighthouses includes participants from 7 non-EU countries, in particular Argentina, Brazil, Chile, India, Kenya, Tanzania and USA. Among these, Argentina and USA (organisations participating in the EU-US Data Privacy Framework) have been recognized by the European Commission as providing adequate data protection.
- For the cases where data privacy adequacy has not been decided by the European Commission, compliance with [GDPR](#) are ensured by requesting contractual agreements between the project coordinator and the non-EU participant, in which the latter should confirm adherence to the requirements of [GDPR](#) (the contractual agreement template will be included in the second version of the data management plan (v2, deliverable D1.8).

Moreover, as regard to TRANS-lighthouses' website (www.trans-lighthouses.eu):

- A Secure Sockets Layer (SSL) certificate was purchased by CES-UC for the address trans-lighthouses.eu in order to encrypt communications between the server and visitors.
- The website clearly communicates its privacy policy and data handling practices, quality and [GDPR](#) policy, including a cookie disclaimer.

Responsible partners and resources

5. Responsible partners and resources

Responsible partners and resources			
Role/Key partners involved	Responsibilities	Resources	
<p>> Project coordinator</p> <p>>> <i>CES-UC</i></p>	<p>> Coordination</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - coordination of communication activities - liaison with partners for content and updates - oversight of dissemination and exploitation efforts - collaboration with partners for consortium and outreach events, exploitation activities <p>> Media outreach</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Press releases, articles, and interviews - Drafting and distribution (collaborative process with partners) <p>> Multimedia content</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - videos and webinars (together with specific tasks outputs) - content creation and production (supported by professional services) - platforms for hosting and dissemination 	<p>> Communication materials</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - templates, fact sheet/project overview, leaflet/flyer, posters, newsletter (supported by professional services) - content creation and production (collaborative process with WP6) <p>> Website (project) [task 1.5]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - design and maintenance - updates and content management (collaborative process with partners) <p>> Social media (supported by professional services)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - LinkedIn, Padlet, YouTube channel - planning: who, how, what, when - content creation, posting and curation - allocate budget for paid advertising or sponsored content - monitor and moderate interactions - compliance with data protection, intellectual property, data ownership - reporting on impact, evolution audience, account/profile, metrics 	<p>>> Other goods and services: allocation of resources to specific activities, channels, tools and materials</p> <p>>> Data base</p> <p>>> Communications agency (FBA)</p> <p>>> Project management office</p> <p>>> Events, communication and image office</p> <p>>> Information technology office</p>
<p>> Steering committee</p> <p>>> <i>CES-UC, RUC, TUM, Cyl, Uni. Eiffel.-CNRS, Athena RC</i></p>	<p>> Coordination</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - collaboratively responsible for the framing and update of the communication, dissemination and exploitation plan, tools, materials and activities - overall responsibility for plan implementation - collaboration with partners for consortium and outreach events, exploitation activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - making the most of internal communication expertise and resources - refinement of KPIs and identification of KERs - liaison with partners for content and updates - transversal operationalisation across key results and WPs 	<p>>> Monthly steering committee meetings</p> <p>>> WPs reporting and planning</p> <p>>> Application to Horizon results Booster</p>
<p>> WP6 participants</p> <p>>> <i>Dedicated to community-based communication and citizen science</i></p> <p>>> <i>Communication and interaction approaches, pathways, channels and tools adapted to local contexts</i></p>	<p>> Coordination</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - communications survey (T1.5 and WP6) - assess communication capabilities/tools/channels of partners - accessible, concrete, actionable and meaningful measures - review and update, ensuring flexibility <p>> Citizen science: setting-up and coordinating reflexive monitoring [T6.1]</p> <p>> Development of resources for action</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - social mobilisation [T6.2] - citizen engagement [T6.2] - NBS communication [T6.2] 	<p>> Communication materials</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - in the framework of T1.5, communication materials are produced in consultation with the participants of WP6 - format and content - aiming at appropriation and adaptation by teams for local use - fine tuning key messages <p>> Website (digital platform, subsites), Social media, Multimedia content [T6.4]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to support the activities of community communication of NBS with youth - including dedicated subsites for each pilot cases 	<p>>> Dedicated tasks and specific outputs of WP6, with corresponding allocated budgets</p> <p>>> Other goods and services</p> <p>>> Collaborative and iterative dynamic with WP5 and WP4 (namely in the development of resources for action)</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - involvement of people with disabilities [task 6.2] [task 6.3] - portfolio of participatory methods [T6.3] - educommunication [T6.4] - digital and low tech tools [T6.5] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - linked to the development of social media and media campaigns > Digital and low tech tools building [T6.5] - to support participatory assessment and data usability - research and assessment results accessible, relevant to audiences and users 	
<p>> Communications contact persons</p> <p><i>>> Identified by each partner</i></p>	<p>> Coordination</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - contact persons identified in communications survey - communicational interface with Task 1.5 and WP6 - support assessment of objectives, environment and communicative capacity of partners - participation in assessment/review workshop - workshop aimed at advancing the communication, dissemination and exploitation plan - support refinement of KPIs and KERs 	<p>> Liaison with the channels and tools of each partner</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - distribute/make available Communication materials - relay messages of Website (pages of partners and their institutions) - relay messages of Social media (pages of partners and their institutions) - relay press releases, articles, and interviews for Media outreach (communication office of partners, mailing lists) - internal sharing of what is happening in the field, with each partner, to celebrate achievements, inspire others, and ask for inspiration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >> Contact list >> Data base >> Surveys and workshops organised by T1.5 and WP6 >> Take advantage of consortium meetings and reflexive monitoring process
<p>> Local partners</p> <p>>> Pilot cases</p> <p><i>Brussels, Rome, Strovolos, Estarreja, Barcelos, Azores, Roskilde, Cáceres</i></p>	<p>> Living Knowledge Labs >> Communication materials >> Events >> Website >> Social media >> Multimedia content >> Media outreach</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - outreach events - collaboration with local stakeholders / exploitation activities - translation of communication materials into local languages provided by the respective consortium partners (Portugal, Denmark, Cyprus, Belgium, Italy, Spain) - targeting local stakeholders, communities, citizens - update of posters 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - videos and webinars (together with specific tasks outputs) - content creation and production. i.e. documentation of the overall design and implementation process of the pilot cases (cross-medial approach) - playbook co-produced with the participants of the 8 pilot cases - subsites and local social media pages managed autonomously - relay the project's messages/posts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >> Living Knowledge Labs >> Digital platform, subsites >> Database >> Dedicated tasks and specific outputs of WP5, allocated budgets >> Other goods and services >> Consortium meetings and technical visits
<p>KPIs</p> <p>PILOT CASES</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 8 posters of pilot cases, updated at least once, translated in local languages - 8 local community events of scientific knowledge dissemination in Living Knowledge Labs - 6 featured project presentations in local media - 3 policy briefs, infographics, videos and serious gaming produced to provide guidance for co-governance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 5 learning cases/dilemmas to be created with local governments and civil society organisations - 2 animated videos on Lab Democracy for NB - 8 dissemination and training workshops, one per pilot - 8 videos, one per pilot, produced by youth - 1 media campaign developed with youth in each lab 	
<p>> Local partners</p> <p>>> Assessment cases</p> <p><i>Brussels, Bologna, Troodos, Estarreja, Barcelos, Lagoa, Regenerative farming network, Madrid, Upper Allgäu, Moisdon-la-Rivière</i></p>	<p>> Communication materials</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - translation into local languages will be provided by the respective consortium partners (Portugal, Denmark, Germany, Cyprus, France, Belgium, Italy, Spain) - update of posters 	<p>> Events, Media outreach and Social media</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - outreach events - exploitation activities - dissemination targeting local stakeholders, communities, citizens - collaboration with local stakeholders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> >> Data base >> Dedicated tasks and specific outputs of WP3, allocated budgets >> Other goods and services >> Consortium meetings and technical visits
<p>SPECIFIC KPIs</p> <p>ASSESSMENT CASES</p>	<p><i>10 posters of assessment cases, updated at least once, translated in local languages</i></p>		

<p>> Local partners >> Associated partners <i>Non-EU based organisations: Chile, Argentina, Brazil, India, USA, Tanzania, Kenya</i></p>	<p>> Communication materials translation of communication materials into local languages provided by the respective associated partners (Chile, Argentina, Brazil, India, USA, Tanzania, Kenya)</p>	<p>> Events, Media outreach and Social media - outreach events - exploitation activities - dissemination targeting local stakeholders, communities, citizens - collaboration with local stakeholders</p>	<p>>> Dedicated task 1.3 and specific outputs, allocated budget >> Other goods and services</p>
<p>SPECIFIC KPIS ASSOCIATED PARTNERS</p>	<p>Participation in activities of the work plan: - in at least 2 webinars per year - in at least 1 technical visit and/or 1 consortium event</p>	<p>- 2 reports based on the compilation and analysis on knowledge sharing and synergies building - at least 1 publication with non-European countries, based on North-South cross comparison</p>	
<p>> All partners >> Art. 17 Grant Agreement >> Transversal operationalisation >> Monitoring, inform and share</p>	<p>> Communication materials [database] - about project based on project's templates and materials - promote action and results, targeted information, multiple audiences - must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag - communication or dissemination activity must indicate disclaimer translated into local languages where appropriate</p> <p>> Transversal operationalisation - activities and outputs across work packages/project's key results - publications in journals/magazines [Monitoring/Inform/Share] - presentations in conferences and in networking events [Monitoring/Inform/Share] - content creation, production, videos, webinars (specific tasks outputs) - outreach events [Monitoring/Inform/Share] - exploitation activities</p>	<p>> Website - contributions to relevant sections of the project's website - at least 2 blog posts in the website per partner during the lifetime of project - the project may rely on the pages of partners and their institutions</p> <p>> Social media - contributions to posts - the project may rely on the pages of partners and their institutions</p> <p>> Media outreach - interviews - connections with journalists and networks - available distribution lists</p>	<p>>> Database >> Dedicated tasks and specific outputs, with corresponding allocated budgets >> Other goods and services >> Consortium meetings and technical visits >> Making the most of internal communication expertise and resources</p>
<p>GENERAL KPIS for ALL PARTNERS</p>	<p>General Communication KPIS: - 3 public communications/exhibitions/workshops in EC events - 3 public communications/sessions/workshops in networking events - 2 blog posts in the project website per partner during the lifetime of the project - 5 press releases in English - 1 institutional video, translated in local languages - 4 media appearances (i.e. TV, radio) - 2 webinars per year (community of practice)</p>	<p>>> For a detailed status report see section 3.3: Key performance indicators and key exploitable results</p>	

Table 39: Responsible partners and resources

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- Horizon Europe Guide on Ethics in Social Sciences and Humanities (2021) https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/ethics-in-social-science-and-humanities_he_en.pdf
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Appendix

Appendix 1: Additional Events & Publication Management Tools

Screenshot of Events attendance planning (tracking of relevant events).

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
1	List of events (CDP: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1ArznTeanQaDPRk8BVAVPlan_B0isohAs/view)	Date	Location	Registration Fees	Call Deadline	Observations	Link for the event
2	EU / European Commission events: (updated 30-07-20)						
3	Europe Day	9th May 2026	Brussels (2025) TBD (2026)				https://core.europa.eu/pl/enqage/Pages/euroopa-day.aspx
4	New European Bauhaus Festival 2026	9-13 June 2026	Brussels		Different calls: 30/09/2025 - 31/12/2025	calls for various forms of participation stands at the Fair - deadline: 30-09-25 Performances and cultural activities at the Fest - deadline:	https://new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/events/festival/
5	European week of regions and cities	28th March 2025					https://regions-and-cities.europa.eu/?pad_source=1&rc
6	Innovation days	3 - 5 February 2025					https://projects.research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/en
7	13th International Conference on Sustainable Development 2025	10-11 September 2025	Rome	-	30 July 2025		https://ec.europa.eu/conference/13th-icad-2025
8							
9	Networking events organised by relevant associations:						
10	ENALL Smart City Expo World Congress (SCEWC)	4-6 November 2025	Barcelona, Spain		12 May 2025		
11	JPI Urban Europe	Calls closed					
12	DUT	TBD			Call opens Sep 2025	Call para projetos	https://dulpartnership.eu/dut-call-2025/
13	- Social Economy European Forum						https://social-economy-call/wayec.europa.eu/useful-re
14	- Gathering of the Global Ecovillage Network of Europe (GEN Europe)	August 12-17th 2025	Manas Garden, Hungary				https://gen-europe.org/news/
15	- Encuentro de Pueblos y Ciudades por la Sostenibilidad de España CONAMA LOCAL 2025	20-22					https://www.fundacionconama.org/que-hacemos/espaa
16	- EUGREEN, European Universities Alliance for Sustainability, responsible Growth, inclusive Education and Environment	Different events (almost every day)			15 November 2024	blended intensive course	https://eugreenalliance.eu/second-call-for-blended-inte
17	- 39a edición Biocultura Madrid y 30a edición Biocultura Barcelona	1-3 May 2025	Barcelona				https://www.biocultura.org/barcelona/informacion
18	- EUROLECS 2025 - Encontro Latino-americano e Europeu sobre Edificações e Comunidades Sustentáveis	1-3 October 2025	Rio de Janeiro		5/11/2024 @ 28/02/2025	submissão ainda em construção	https://www.eurolecs.org/br/
19	CULTURS Conference: Por uma resiliência criativa? Re-imaginando culturas urbanas, sociabilidades e participação	14-15 November 2024	Coimbra				
20	NetworkNature Science-Policy Dialogue	15th September 2025	Brussels				More info coming soon
21	NetworkNature Annual Event "Choose nature"	16th September 2025	Brussels				https://www.tickettailor.com/events/sucn/166900
22							
23	International and referenced conferences						
24	- ISA World Congress of Sociology	4-10 July 2027	Gwangju, Korea	Not available information	Not available information		https://www.isa-sociology.org/en/conferences/world-c
25	- EURA Conference	15-19 April 2025	Vancouver, BC, Canada	Individual Member - \$405 USD (370€)	October 1, 2024 (11:59pm CDT)		https://eura.org/conferences/
26	- NESS					Not available information for 2025	
27				Registration fopen in	Submission of abstracts will open		

Screenshot of Dissemination and communication tracking: Organization and attendance of events.

This section MUST be filled according to instructions below:															
Technical Reporting		Technical reporting													
Type of scientific event	Organization of event: Organisers) (Year, Event Title (Edition, if applicable), Location, Date. Presentation in event: Authors) (Year), Title of the presentation, Paper/poster presented at Conference Name, Location, Date.	Dissemination activity name	Date of dissemination	Partner Responsible/Participating	Organizer Name	Location (city, country)	What? Type of Dissemination Activity	Who? Target Audience Reached	Event-related links (external or internal)	Status of the Dissemination Activity	Total number of registered participants	Number of Male participants	Number of Female participants		
Organization of scientific event	CES & TUM. (2023) Network Nature Annual Meeting Brussels, Belgium, 7-9 June 2023.	Network Nature Annual Meeting Brussels	7-9/6/2023	CES, TUM	Network Nature	Brussels	Clustering activities	EU Institutions		Delivered	around 200	Equal	Equal		
Organization of scientific event	CES & TUM. (2024) URBINAT Final Conference, Porto, Portugal, 6-8 March 2024.	URBINAT Final Conference	6-8/3/2024	CES, TUM	URBINAT	Porto	Collaboration with EU-funded	Other		Delivered	around 50 in session	Equal	Equal		
Presentation in scientific event	CES & TUM. (2024) CoEvolvers Beskydy Workshop, Velke Karlovice, Czech Republic, 24-26 Spetember 2024.	CoEvolvers Beskydy Workshop	24-26/9/2024	CES, TUM	CoEvolvers	Velke Karlovice (CZ)	Clustering activities	Other	https://www.beskydy2024.eu/	Delivered	Around 40-50	Equal	Equal		
Presentation in scientific event	CES & TUM. (2023) Clever Cities Final Conference Hamburg, Germany, 25-28 September 2023.	Clever Cities Final Conference	25-28/9/2023	CES, TUM	EU-H Clever Cities Project	Hamburg	Collaboration with EU-funded	Other		Delivered	around 200 in panel discussion, 40 in session	Equal	Equal		
Organization of scientific event	CMB (2024) Awareness-raising Workshop Play, Risk and Nature. Vila Cova - Barcelos, Portugal, 12 June 2024.	Awareness-raising Workshop Play, Risk and Nature	12/06/2024	CMB	CMB	Vila Cova - Barcelos	Education and training events	Other		Delivered	26	4	22	0	
Organization of scientific event	CMB (2024) Awareness-raising Workshop Play, Risk and Nature. Vila Seca - Barcelos, Portugal, 22 May 2024.	Awareness-raising Workshop Play, Risk and Nature	22/05/2024	CMB	CMB	Vila Seca - Barcelos	Education and training events	Other		Delivered	12	2	10	0	
Organization of scientific event	CMB (2024) Awareness-raising Workshop Play, Risk and Nature. VFS, Martinho - Barcelos, Portugal, 29 May 2024.	Awareness-raising Workshop Play, Risk and Nature	29 may 2024	CMB	CMB	VFS, Martinho - Barcelos	Education and training events	Other		Delivered	18	2	16	0	
Organization of scientific event	CMB & CES (2024) Awareness-raising Workshop NbS and Climate Changes. Vila Cova - Barcelos, Portugal, 22 March 2024.	Awareness-raising Workshop NbS and Climate Changes	22/03/2024	CMB, CES	CMB	Vila Cova - Barcelos	Education and training events	Other		Delivered	30	7	23	0	
Organization of scientific event	CMB & CES (2024) Awareness-raising Workshop NbS and Climate Changes. VFS, Martinho - Barcelos, Portugal, 27 March 2024.	Awareness-raising Workshop NbS and Climate Changes	27/03/2024	CMB, CES	CMB	VFS, Martinho - Barcelos	Education and training events	Other		Delivered	26	2	24	0	
Organization of scientific event	CMB & CES (2024) Awareness-raising Workshop NbS and Climate Changes. Vila Seca - Barcelos, Portugal, 27 March 2024.	Awareness-raising Workshop NbS and Climate Changes	27/03/2024	CMB, CES	CMB	Vila Seca - Barcelos	Education and training events	Other		Delivered	11	3	8	0	
Organization of scientific event	CMB, CES, Kairos. (2024) Awareness-raising Workshop Participatory Methods and Participatory Budget. Vila Cova - Barcelos, Portugal, 19 June 2024.	Awareness-raising Workshop Participatory Methods and Participatory Budget	19/06/2024	CMB, CES, Kairos	CMB	Vila Cova - Barcelos	Education and training events	Other		Delivered	17	2	15	0	

Screenshot of Mapping of publication channels document.

Types of publication	Selection of publications/media	Cost (USDS)	Score	H-index
Open research platforms	Horizon Results Platform			
Open access publications	Global Environmental Change (<i>Elsevier</i>)	\$5530	IF: 8.6	
International referenced publications (scientific, technical, architect, environmental journals)	Environment and Behavior (<i>Sage</i>)	00139165, 1552390X	\$3700	IF: 5.2
	Environment and Planning A (<i>Sage</i>)	0308518X, 14723409	\$3700	
	Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment (<i>Elsevier</i>)	01678809	\$3840	IF: 6.0
	Nature-based solutions (<i>Elsevier</i>)	2772-4115	\$1800	? n/f
Publications with processing charge/fee afforded by the project to grant free access to Readers	Environmental Monitoring and Assessment (<i>Springer</i>)	01676369, 15732959	\$3890	142
	Environment and Planning D: Society and Space (<i>Sage</i>)	02637758, 14723433	\$3700	124
	Critical Reviews in Environmental Science and Technology (<i>Taylor & Francis</i>)	10643389, 15476537	\$	144
	Psychosocial Intervention (<i>JCR (Q1), IF 4.8</i>)	11320559, 21734712		32
	Social Inclusion (<i>JCR, IF 1.5</i>)	n/f SJR		
	Arquitecturas del Sur	n/f SJR		

Screenshot of Central management tool for organizing publication opportunities (per deliverable).

Name	Status	D5.5	NBS LKL Playbook	Status	D6.2	Data usability	Status	D6.4	Catalogue of participatory methods	Status	D6.5	Citizen science global framework for NBS	Status	D6.6
A. Umantseva		None	null		None	null		None	null		None	null		None
G. Artopoulos		Both o...	Co-aut...		Both o...	Co-aut...		None	null		None	null		Both o...
C. Spanos		Both o...	Co-aut...		Both o...	Co-aut...		None	null		None	null		Both o...
J. Santos		None	null		None	null		None	null		None	null		None
A. Lundgren		None	null		None	null		Public...	Co-aut...	Planned	Both o...	Co-aut...	Planned	None
A. Barbas		None	null		None	null		None	null		None	null		None
I.Ferreira		None	null		None	null		None	null		Public...	Lead ...		None
		None	null		None	null		None	null		None	null		None
		None	null		None	null		None	null		None	null		None
		None	null		None	null		None	null		None	null		None
		None	null		None	null		None	null		None	null		None
		None	null		None	null		None	null		None	null		None
		None	null		None	null		None	null		None	null		None

Screenshots of Central management tool for organizing publication opportunities (per dissemination type)

Deliverable	Journal article / online publication	Journal article	Journal article	Conference paper / presentation	Conference paper / presentation	Conference paper / presentation
	A. Umantseva	A. Umantseva	A. Umantseva	A. Umantseva	A. Umantseva	A. Umantseva
D2.4	journal name /publisher & possible date	journal name /publisher & possible date	journal name /publisher & possible date	conference name & details	conference name & details	conference name & details
	A. Umantseva	A. Umantseva	A. Umantseva	A. Umantseva	A. Umantseva	A. Umantseva
D2.5 Guide on research ethics & inclusive participations for NBS	Frontiers February 2026			Degrowth Conference July 2026		
	Barbas, Andreia			Barbas, Andreia		
	Santos, Joana			Santos, Joana		
	Ferreira, Isabel			Ferreira, Isabel		
	Lupp, Gerd			Lupp, Gerd		
	Ela Callorda			Ela Callorda		
	Spanos, Charalampos			Spanos, Charalampos		
	Kritiotis, Constantinos			Kritiotis, Constantinos		
	Anna Umantseva			Anna Umantseva		
D3.2 Report on Recommendations given and Lessons learned from the Case Analyses	[to think about the indicators section] March 2026			Terraenvision July 2025		

Table 40: Additional Events & Publication Management Tools.

Appendix 2: References for Key Performance Indicators

Publications	
Books	European Commission - Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Andersson, I., Ferreira, I., Arlati, A., Bradley, S. et al. (2023). <i>Guidelines for co-creation and co-governance of nature-based solutions – Insights from EU-funded projects</i> , Ferreira, I.(editor), Lupp, G.(editor) and Mahmoud, I.(editor), Publications Office of the European Union https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/157060
Papers in Conference Proceedings	Lupp, G., Ferreira, I., Nunes, N., Caitana, B., Marques, E., Canto Moniz, G. (2024). Forests and transformative governance - Insights from TRANS-lighthouses. In <i>Book of Abstracts, IUFRO 2024, Sweden, 23-29 June 2024</i> , p. 2776. Swedish Agricultural University.
	Spanos, C., Artopoulos, G. Constantinos Kritiotis, Afroditi Magou (2025). 'Strovolos' TRANS-lighthouse: A roadmap towards sustainable, just, and inclusive NBS.' Urgent Pedagogies UP, <i>Reader of the 2024 Conference Learnings/Unlearnings: Environmental Pedagogies, Play, Policies, and Spatial Design</i> . KTH School of Architecture, Stockholm.
	Lundgren, A., Gouveia, P., Nunes, N., & Campos, R. (2025). [Forthcoming]. Developing a collaborative portfolio of participatory methods for NBS governance: The TRANS-lighthouses approach. In <i>The CULTURS International Colloquium "For Creative Resilience? Reimagining Urban Cultures, Sociability, and Participation"</i> , Cescontexto, 37, November 2025.
	Ottaviani, D. (2025). " A green classroom for the university community at large: the experience of the Horizon project TRANS-lighthouses at Sapienza Campus". ISBN: 978-88-7603-269-1
Articles in Scientific Journals	[Forthcoming]. Gallén-Granell, E., & Marques, E. (2025). Nature as a bridge: Forest mind as an ecosocial work practice for homelessness. <i>Journal of Evidence-Based Social Work</i> . https://doi.org/10.1080/26408066.2025.2560076
Other Publications	Davis, M; Cuevas, NB; Lupp, G; Maestre-Andres, S; Xidous, D; Zingraff-Hamed, A. (2025). <i>Including commonly excluded stakeholders in NbS co-creation processes: Workshop background document</i> . NetworkNature+ Task Force 6., 28 p.
Publication with processing fee	Caitana, B., Callorda, E., Lemaitre, A., Ruiz Rivera, M. J., & Umantseva, A. (2004). Repensando las "Soluciones basadas en la Naturaleza" desde el pensamiento post-desarrollista latinoamericano. <i>Revista de la Academia</i> , (38). https://doi.org/10.25074/0196318.38.2811

Table 41: Key Performance Indicators references - Publications.

Webinars	
Internal webinars:	
	UGE - CNRS. (2023). Introduction to reflexive Monitoring and material presentation. Task 6.1.
	UGE - CNRS. (2024). First year's learning outcomes: statistics; actions or productions in line with WPs outlines, Learning outcomes, partners feelings regarding the project's evolution since its beginning, ongoing aspects of the project and next steps. Task 6.1.
	UGE - CNRS. (2024). Identifying Critical Turning points.Task 6.1.
	Jangada. (2023-2024). Educommunication. Task 6.4.
	Jangada. (2023-2024). Democratic Spaces for Dialogue. Task 6.4.
	Jangada. (2023-2024). Awareness Campaigns. Task 6.4.

Jangada. (2023-2024). Media and Journalism Skills. Task 6.4.
Jangada. (2023-2024). Photography for Advocacy. Task 6.4.
Jangada. (2023-2024). Social Media Engagement. Task 6.4.
Jangada. (2023-2024). Podcast Production). Task 6.4.
Steering Committee. (2024). Aligning the Conceptual Framework with WP3 Assessment Cases. Task 2.1.
Steering Committee. (2024). Aligning the Conceptual Framework with WP4 Participatory Governance Activities. Task 2.1.
Steering Committee. (2024). Developing Roadmaps and Co-creation Methods for Pilot Cases. Tasks 5.1, 5.2, 5.3.
Steering Committee. (2024). Literature Review Search Validation and Initial Outcomes.
Steering Committee. (2024). Ontology. Task T3.2.
Steering Committee. (2024). Assisting Pilots in Selecting Appropriate Co-design Tools. Task 5.2, T5.5.
Transformative Economies Task Force. (2024). Paradigmatic Transitions Practices.
CES & TUM (2025) Reflection on Indicators and Selection for TRL Cases. Task 3.3.
CES. (2025). Webinar on Data Collection Process. Task 3.3
Steering Committee. (2025). Management and Documentation of Implementation Activities for Communication. Task 5.3.
Steering Committee. (2025). Assessment for the Development of a PPGIS Platform. Tasks 5.5, 6.5, 3.5.
Open webinars:
UCL. (2024). UNLEARNING AND CRITICAL APPROACHES TO NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS: Unlearning spaces for transformative change to sustainability: insights from Community Supported Agriculture (CSA) in the Netherlands. Task 2.4.
UCL. (2024). UNLEARNING AND CRITICAL APPROACHES TO NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS: Nature, biodiversity, and the politics of difference. Task 2.4.
UCL. (2024). UNLEARNING AND CRITICAL APPROACHES TO NATURE-BASED SOLUTIONS: Deconstructing Epistemological Hierarchies: Unlearning and Relearning through Participatory Co-production of Knowledges. Task T2.4.
CES. (2025). Eco feminism & Nature-based Solutions.
CES. (2025). Social Solidarity Economy.
CES. (2025). Education & Nature-based Solutions.
Year 3 (planned)
Transformative governance. [Public webinar]. M35.
Rural-urban communities & human-nature cultures. [Public webinar]. M35.

Nature based tourism. [Public webinar]. M35.

Table 42: Key Performance Indicators references - Webinars.

Featured project presentations in local media

Hoy. Arroyo de la Luz. (2024). Seminar "Mater Composta": Methodology Menú Mater and technical visit to the proto living lab of Arroyo de la Luz (Cáceres province). <https://arroyodelaluz.hoy.es/seminario-mater-composta-formo-varias-personas-sobre-20240511122134-nt.html>

Radio Interior(2024). Cáceres presents its model of Citizen Participation in Rome at the III Meeting of the Trans-lighthouses Consortium. Canal Extremadura, Spain. <https://www.radiointerior.es/texto-diario/mostrar/4875736/caceres-expone-en-roma-su-modelo-de-participacion-ciudadana>

Diário de Aveiro. (2025). *Launch of Co-Diagnostic Sessions for the Estarreja Pilot Case (ECO – Estarreja Colaborativa e Orientadora)*. <https://www.diarioaveiro.pt/2025/01/17/municipio-vai-ouvir-as-populacoes-para-bem-gerir-a-natureza/>

AveiroMag. (2025). *Launch of Co-Diagnostic Sessions for the Estarreja Pilot Case (ECO – Estarreja Colaborativa e Orientadora)*. <https://www.aveiromag.pt/artigo?a=6788&estarreja-da-eco-comunidade>

The Portugal News. (2025). *Launch of Co-Diagnostic Sessions for the Estarreja Pilot Case (ECO – Estarreja Colaborativa e Orientadora)*. <https://www.theportugalnews.com/pt/noticias/2025-09-23/aveiro-acolhe-projeto-de-conservacao-dinamica/185622>

Table 43: Key Performance Indicators references - Featured project presentations in local media.

Media Appearances (TV, Radio)

Radio Interior. (2024). *Cáceres presents its model of Citizen Participation in Rome at the III Meeting of the Trans-lighthouses Consortium*. Spain. <https://www.radiointerior.es/texto-diario/mostrar/4875736/caceres-expone-en-roma-su-modelo-de-participacion-ciudadana>

Canal Extremadura. (2024). *New life through agroecology and compost in Carcaboso*. Spain. <http://www.canalextramadura.es/video/una-nueva-vida-gracias-a-la-agroecologia>

RMC – Radio Marie Christine. (2024). *Presentation of TRANS-Lighthouses Project and youth podcast from the Training in Trento*. Belgium. <https://www.radiomariechristine.be/creations-rmc/>

Radio Sapienza. (2025). *Workshop "NBS for Public Space. Green Classrooms for the II Municipality of Rome."* <https://www.radiosapienza.net/aule-verdi-nel-2o-municipio-il-workshop-sapienza/>

Radio Interior. (2024). *Cáceres presents its model of Citizen Participation in Rome at the III Meeting of the Trans-lighthouses Consortium*. Spain. <https://www.radiointerior.es/texto-diario/mostrar/4875736/caceres-expone-en-roma-su-modelo-de-participacion-ciudadana>

Canal Extremadura. (2024). *New life through agroecology and compost in Carcaboso*. Spain. <http://www.canalextramadura.es/video/una-nueva-vida-gracias-a-la-agroecologia>

TVC Sapó. (2025). *Launch of Co-Diagnostic Sessions for the Estarreja Pilot Case (ECO – Estarreja Colaborativa e Orientadora)*. <https://tvc.sapo.pt/2025/01/14/projeto-eco-estarreja-colaborativa-e-orientadora/>

Porto Canal. (2025). *Launch of Co-Diagnostic Sessions for the Estarreja Pilot Case (ECO – Estarreja Colaborativa e Orientadora)*. <https://portocanal.sapo.pt/noticia/360159>

Table 44: Key Performance Indicators references - Media Appearances (TV, Radio).

Pilot introduction of NBS co-creation and co-governance content in college disciplines

UNIROMA1. (2023). OyePadu Podcast - Colegio Paideuterion. Cáceres, Spain, 3 December 2023.

UNIROMA1. (2024). The context of intervention for the Rome Pilot. Presentation at the Sapienza Campus. Rome, Italy, February 2024.

CME. (2024). Presentation at PACOPAR's plenary session. Estarreja, Portugal, 28 March 2024.

CES. (2024). Co-creating with Nature: socio-political solutions for climate adaptation. Faculty of Economics of the University of Coimbra.

UEx. (2024). Ciência Circular. Composting Chefs: Cooking Organic Waste to Feed the Earth. Licenciados Reunidos School. Cáceres, Spain, 3 December 2024.

UNIROMA (2025) A green classroom for the university community at large: the experience of the Horizon project TRANS-lighthouses at Sapienza Campus. GUD Genealogy on Urban Design DICEA Sapienza: Public Spaces for Community Campuses and Universities.

Table 45: Key Performance Indicators references -Pilot introduction of NBS co-creation and co-governance content in college disciplines.

Public communications/ sessions/workshops in networking events

CES & TUM. (2023). Network Nature Annual Meeting Brussels, Belgium, 7-9 June 2023.

UEx. (2023). Rethinking Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) in Europe through transdisciplinary research: A learning/unlearning perspective. Louvain-la-Neuve, Belgium, 24 November 2023.

CES & TUM. (2023). Clever Cities Final Conference. Hamburg, Germany, 25-28 September 2023.

CYI. (2024). CeOS_SE Project Symposium. Nicosia, Cyprus, 18 October 2024.

Jangada. (2024). Contribution to "Virtual University" Open Online Training Course on "Healthy and sustainable cities for the future". Munich, Germany, 14 May 2024.

TUM. (2024). Presentation of TRL and WP3/Upper Allgäu Assessment Case. Presented at ESP (Ecosystem Partnership) Conference. Wageningen, Netherlands, 18-22 December 2024.

TUM & CES. (2024). First insights to forest related NBSs. Presented at IUFRO World Congress. Stockholm, Sweden, 23-29 June 2024.

UEx & EBR. (2024). European Researcher's Night - Young composters: Regenerating soil through composting. Cáceres, Spain, 27 September 2024.

UCLouvain. (2024). Rethinking NBS with marginalised economic knowledge: a transdisciplinary approach. Pontevedra, Spain, 20 June 2024.

Table 46: Key Performance Indicators references - Networking events.

Steering committee: 6 participations of partners in national, regional and international events

CES. (2024). TRANS-Lighthouses Governance Framework. Presentation at NESS Conference. Turku, Finland, June 2024.

CES. (2025) Co-criar com a natureza: experiências de investigação-ação. Presentation at Ciência 2025 - Meeting with Science and Technology, NOVA SBE Campus, Carcavelos, Portugal. July 2025

TUM, VBX. UCLouvain& CES. (2025). Network Nature Annual event: Choose nature, Brussels, Belgium, September 2025.

CES (2025) NBS Project Board. Network Nature+, Online, March 2025

CES (2025) NBS Project Board. Network Nature+, Online, June 2025

CES (2025) NBS Project Board. Network Nature+, Online, September 2025

RUC. (2024). Developing transdisciplinary research capacities to advance the SE field in the face of multidimensional crises. Exploring the different facets of the social and solidarity economy and social innovation. Presentation at the 9th EMES International Training School. Trento, Italy, June 2024.

CES, TUM, VBX. & UCLouvain (2024). Network Nature Annual Meeting Brussels, Belgium, September 2024.

CES. (2025). Placemaking Week Europe. Placemaking gaming session. Italy, 23 September 2025.

TUM, VBX, CES. & UCLouvain (2025). Network Nature Annual Meeting Brussels: Networking event, Belgium, September 2025.

CES (2025) Transformative Change for Biodiversity Cluster Workshop. European Research Executive Agency; Directorate-General for Research and Innovation; e European Research Council Executive Agency, Brussels, Belgium.

CES & TUM (2025): Measuring What Matters: Co-Creation Indicators for the Socio-Political Dimensions of Nature-Based Solutions. TERRAeVISION Conference, Granada, Spain, July 2025

CES & TUM. (2024). CoEvolvers Beskydy Workshop. Velke Karlovice, Czech Republic, 24-26 September 2024.

Table 47: Key Performance Indicators references -Participation of partners in national, regional and international events

Public communications/ exhibitions/workshops in EC events

EBR, UEX & UCLouvain. (2024). Cyprus European Researchers Night 2024. Nicosia, Cyprus, September 2024.

UEx & EBR. (2024). European Researcher's Night - Young composters: Regenerating soil through composting. Cáceres, Spain, September 2024.

CES. (2025). Transformative Change for Biodiversity Cluster Workshop. Brussels, June 2025.

Table 48: Key Performance Indicators references - Public communications/ exhibitions/workshops in EC events.

International and referenced conferences

CYI. (2024). Local Democracy Academy. Lund, Sweden, 26 August 2024.

UEx. (2024). Living Knowledge Labs (LKLs) as a strategy of "community-based degrowth" (CBD) through Nature-Based Solutions on decentralized composting. Presented at the 10th International Degrowth Conference - Vigo, Spain, June 2024.

UEx. (2024). VII Agroecological Encounter in Torremocha del Jarama: "CSA as a lighthouse for ecosocial transition". Torremocha del Jarama, Spain, September 2024.

UCLouvain. (2024). Rethinking NBS with marginalised economic knowledge: "Towards a transformative diversity, Lisbon, Portugal, November 2024.

EBR. (2024). Towards Reciprocal Human-Nature Relationships in Nature Based Solutions?<presented at the 4th International Conference Social and Solidarity Economy and the Commons. Lisbon, Portugal, November 2024.

RUC. (2024). Keynote presentation at the 4th International Conference Social and Solidarity Economy and the Commons. Lisbon, Portugal, November 2024.

CES (2025). From Tokenism to Transformation: Opportunities, challenges, and risks in participatory Nature-Based Solutions for a just and sustainable future. Abstract presented at the 16th International Sustainability Transitions (IST) Conference 2025, Lisbon, Portugal, June, 2025.

TUM (2025). Forests and Forest Management as NBS: Lessons learned from Co-Creation processes in Upper Allgäu (Germany). TERRAeVISION Conference, Granada, Spain, July 2025

TUM (2025). The socio-cultural and socio-political dimensions of NBS and the relevance of Social Sciences and Humanities for mainstreaming NBS TERRAeVISION Conference, Granada, Spain, July 2025

Table 49: Key Performance Indicators references - International and referenced conferences.

Local community events of scientific knowledge dissemination in Living Knowledge Labs

CMB. (2024). Awareness-raising Workshop Play, Risk and Nature. Vila Cova - Barcelos, Portugal, June 2024.

CMB. (2024). Awareness-raising Workshop Play, Risk and Nature. Vila Seca - Barcelos, Portugal, May 2024.

CMB. (2024). Awareness-raising Workshop Play, Risk and Nature. VFS. Martinho - Barcelos, Portugal, May 2024.

CMB & CES. (2024). Awareness-raising Workshop NbS and Climate Changes. Vila Cova - Barcelos, Portugal, March 2024.

CMB & CES. (2024). Awareness-raising Workshop NbS and Climate Changes. VFS. Martinho- Barcelos, Portugal, March 2024.

CMB & CES. (2024). Awareness-raising Workshop NBS and Climate Changes. Vila Seca - Barcelos, Portugal, March 2024.

CMB, CES, Kairós. (2024). Awareness-raising Workshop Participatory Methods and Participatory Budget. Vila Cova - Barcelos, Portugal, June 2024.

CMB, CES, Kairós. (2024). Awareness-raising Workshop Participatory Methods and Participatory Budget. VFS. Martinho - Barcelos, Portugal, May 2024.

CMB, CES, Kairós. (2024). Awareness-raising Workshop Participatory Methods and Participatory Budget. Vila Seca - Barcelos, Portugal, May 2024.

CNRS. (2023). Visit and participatory workshop 1: researchers-pioneers. Moisdon-La-Rivière, France, May 2023.

CNRS. (2023). Visit and participatory workshop 2: researchers-pioneers-youth. Moisdon-La-Rivière, France, October 2023.

CNRS. (2023). Visit and participatory workshop 2: researchers-pioneers-youth. Moisdon-La-Rivière, France, October 2023.

CYI. (2024). Happiness Fair. Strovolos, Cyprus, April 2024.

CYI. (2024). "sCYence Fair 2024": Empowering Tomorrow Through Youth Innovation. Aglantzia, Cyprus, April 2024.

CYI. (2024). The Cyprus Institute Innovation Bootcamp for TREATY. Strovolos, Cyprus, June 2024.

CYI. (2024). Learnings/Unlearnings: Environmental Pedagogies, Play, Policies, and Spatial Design. Stockholm, Sweden, September 2024.

CYI. (2024). TRANS-lighthouse CurioCity. Strovolos, Cyprus, June 2024.

CYI. (2024). Co-diagnostic Workshop. Strovolos, Cyprus, July 2024.

CYI. (2024). (Un)Learning Workshop. Strovolos, Cyprus, September 2024.

EBR. (2024). Seminar Mater Composta. Arroyo de la Luz, Spain, April 2024.

EBR & UEX. (2024). 13th Spanish composting gathering. Cáceres, Spain, October 2024.

UEX & EBR. (2024). Composting Knowledge Community. Cáceres, Spain, September 2024.

EBR. (2024). Composting Knowledge Community. Cáceres, Spain, September 2024.

EBR. (2024). Challenges of Biowaste Management change through Decentralised Composting. Cáceres, Spain, May 2024.

VBX. (2024). Walkthrough. Brussels, Belgium, June 2024.

VBX. (2024). Photovoice. Brussels, Belgium, July 2024.

VBX. (2024). Presentation of Municipal Water Plan and Green Primes on the water bus. Brussels, Belgium, June 2024.

VBX. (2024). Awareness-raising workshop: "Flooding in Laeken: a shower of solutions". Brussels, Belgium, September 2024.
VBX. (2024). Awareness-raising visit: Sewer museum visit. Brussels, Belgium, September 2024.
VBX. (2024). Learning-unlearning workshop from citizens from Jette. Brussels, Belgium, October 2024.
VBX. (2024). Door to door campaign. Brussels, Belgium, September 2024.
VBX. (2024). Composting Workshop - IES Brocense. Cáceres, Spain, April 2024.
UEx & EBR. (2024). Desayuna con la ciencia - Composting Workshop: Message in a bottle. Cáceres, Spain, April 2024.
UEx. (2024). 13th Composta en Red Seminar: Living Knowledge Lab. Cáceres, Spain, October 2024.
UCLouvain. (2024). Unlearning spaces for transformative change to sustainability. Louvain-la-Neuve, Belgium, April 2024.
UCLouvain. (2024). Deconstructing Epistemological Hierarchies. Louvain-la-Neuve, Belgium, October 2024.
UCLouvain. (2024). Gamified workshops with students. Vila Cova, Barcelos, Portugal, November 2024.
EBR. (2024). Seminar Mater Composta with Menú Mater tool/methodology. Arroyo de la Luz, Spain, April 2024.
EBR. (2024). Seminar Mater Composta with Menú Mater tool/methodology. Arroyo de la Luz, Spain, April 2024.
UAc. (2024). Citizen Science exploration activity. Azores, Portugal, April 2024.
UAc. (2024). Awareness-raising Workshop Play, Risk, Nature and biodiversity. Azores, Portugal, April 2024.
UAc. (2024). Walkthrough in the local Remédios. Azores, Portugal, November 2024.
UAc. (2024). Cultural Mapping. Azores, Portugal, November 2024.
CME. (2024). Kick-off - school-based LKL (11th grade). Estarreja, Portugal, November 2024.
CME. (2024). Kick-off - school-based LKL (8th grade). Avanca - Estarreja, Portugal, December 2024.
CME. (2024). Kick-off - school-based LKL (8th grade). Pardilhó - Estarreja, Portugal, July 2024.
CMB. (2025). The world outside - Pilot school Student workshop. Barcelos, Portugal, January-June 2025.
CMB & CES. (2024). Workshops with students about NbS (introducing the Board Game).

Table 50: Key Performance Indicators references - Local community events of scientific knowledge dissemination in Living Knowledge Labs.